

**To Study the Impact of Personality Type and Gender on Smartphone
Addiction and Social Competence of Young Adults**

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Table of Contents

Chapter	Title	Page Number
I	Abstract	XI
1	Introduction	1 - 17
1.1	Personality	1
1.2	Smartphone Addiction	8
1.3	Social Competence	13
2	Review of Literature	18 - 42
3	Research Methodology	43 - 61
3.1	Introduction	43
3.2	Title of the Study	43
3.3	Objectives	43
3.4	Null Hypotheses	46
3.5	Variables	50
3.6	Research Design	50
3.7	Selection of Sample	52
3.8	Procedure	53
3.9	Research Tools	54
3.10	Statistical Tools	59
4	Results and Discussion	62 - 136
5	Conclusion	137-143
5.1	Summary	137
5.2	Conclusions	137
5.3	Implications	141
5.4	Limitations	141
5.5	Recommendations	142
	References	1 - 7
	Appendices	1 - 9

List of Tables

Table Number	Title	Page number
3.1	The independent variables and the dependent variables of the study	50
3.2	Research Design of the study for Smartphone Addiction	51
3.3	Research Design of the study for Social Competence	51
3.4	Scoring for Type A/B Behavioural Pattern Scale	55
3.5	Dimensions of Form A	55
3.6	Dimensions of Form B	56
3.7	Scoring for Smartphone Addiction Scale	57
3.8	Interpretation of Smartphone Addiction Scale	57
3.9	Scoring for Social Competence Scale	58
3.10	Interpretation of Social Competence Scale	58
3.11	The Analysis of Data	59
4.1	Summary of Correlation for Smartphone Addiction total and Social Competence Total	62
4.2	Summary of comparison of means of social competence in context of personality type.	64
4.3	Summary of comparison of means of social competence in context of gender.	66
4.4	Summary of Two-way ANOVA for Smartphone Addiction in context of Personality Type and Gender	69
4.5	Summary of Mean Scores of Smartphone Addiction among Males by Personality Type	73
4.6	Summary of Mean Scores of Smartphone Addiction among Females by Personality Type	75
4.7	Summary of Mean Scores of Social Competence among Males by Personality Type	77
4.8	Summary of Mean Scores of Social Competence among Females by Personality Type	79
4.9	Summary of Mean Scores of Compulsion by Gender	81
4.10	Summary of Mean Scores of Forgetfulness by Gender	82

4.11	Summary of Mean Scores of Lack of Attention by Gender	84
4.12	Summary of Mean Scores of Depression & Anxiety by Gender	86
4.13	Summary of Mean Scores of Disturbed Hunger/Sleep by Gender	87
4.14	Summary of Mean Scores of Social Withdrawal by Gender	89
4.15	Summary of Mean Scores of Personal Adequacy by Gender	91
4.16	Summary of Mean Scores of Interpersonal Adequacy by Gender	93
4.17	Summary of Mean Scores of Communication Skills by Gender	95
4.18	Summary of Mean Scores of Compulsion by Personality Type	97
4.19	Summary of Mean Scores of Forgetfulness by Personality Type	99
4.20	Summary of Mean Scores of Lack of Attention by Personality Type	101
4.21	Summary of Mean Scores of Depression & Anxiety by Personality Type	102
4.22	Summary of Mean Scores of Disturbed Hunger/Sleep by Personality Type	104
4.23	Summary of Mean Scores of Social Withdrawal by Personality Type	106
4.24	Summary of Mean Scores of Personal Adequacy by Personality Type	108
4.25	Summary of Mean Scores of Interpersonal Adequacy by Personality Type	110
4.26	Summary of Mean Scores of Communication Skills by Personality Type	112
4.27	Summary of Correlation between Compulsion and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills	114
4.28	Summary of Correlation between Forgetfulness and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills	117
4.29	Summary of Correlation between Lack of Attention and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills	121
4.30	Summary of Correlation between Depression & Anxiety and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills	125

4.31	Summary of Correlation between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills	128
4.32	Summary of Correlation between Social Withdrawal and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills	132

List of Graphs

Graph Number	Title	Page Number
4.1	Graphical representation showing correlation between smartphone addiction and social competence.	63
4.2	Graphical representation of comparison of means of social competence in context of personality type.	65
4.3	Graphical representation of comparison of means of social competence in context of gender.	67
4.4	Graphical representation of comparison of means of smartphone addiction in context of Personality Type	69
4.5	Graphical representation of comparison of means of smartphone addiction in context of Gender.	70
4.6	Graphical representation of comparison of means of smartphone addiction among males in context of Gender.	73
4.7	Graphical representation of comparison of means of smartphone addiction among females	76
4.8	Graphical representation of comparison of means of social competence among males in context of Personality type	78
4.9	Graphical representation of comparison of means of social competence among females in context of Personality type.	80
4.10	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Compulsion in context of Gender.	82
4.11	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Forgetfulness in context of Gender.	83

4.12	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Lack of Attention in context of Gender.	85
4.13	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Depression and Anxiety in context of Gender.	86
4.14	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Disturbed Hunger/Sleep in context of Gender.	88
4.15	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Withdrawal in context of Gender.	90
4.16	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Personal Adequacy in context of Gender.	91
4.17	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Interpersonal Adequacy in context of Gender.	93
4.18	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Communication Skills in context of Gender.	95
4.19	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Compulsion in context of Personality Type.	98
4.20	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Forgetfulness in context of Personality Type.	100
4.21	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Lack of Attention in context of Personality Type.	101
4.22	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Depression and Anxiety in context of Personality Type.	103
4.23	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Disturbed Hunger/Sleep in context of Personality Type.	105
4.24	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Withdrawal in context of Personality Type.	107
4.25	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Personal Adequacy in context of Personality Type.	108
4.26	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Interpersonal Adequacy in context of Personality Type.	110
4.27	Graphical representation of comparison of means of Communication Skills in context of Personality Type.	112
4.28	Graphical representation showing correlation between compulsion and personal adequacy.	114

4.29	Graphical representation showing correlation between compulsion and interpersonal adequacy.	115
4.30	Graphical representation showing correlation between compulsion and communication skills.	115
4.31	Graphical representation showing correlation between forgetfulness and personal adequacy.	118
4.32	Graphical representation showing correlation between forgetfulness and interpersonal adequacy.	118
4.33	Graphical representation showing correlation between forgetfulness and communication skills.	119
4.34	Graphical representation showing correlation between lack of attention and personal adequacy.	122
4.35	Graphical representation showing correlation between lack of attention and interpersonal adequacy.	122
4.36	Graphical representation showing correlation between lack of attention and communication skill.	123
4.37	Graphical representation showing correlation between depression & anxiety and personal adequacy.	125
4.38	Graphical representation showing correlation between depression & anxiety and interpersonal adequacy.	126
4.39	Graphical representation showing correlation between depression & anxiety and communication skill.	126
4.40	Graphical representation showing correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep and personal adequacy.	129
4.41	Graphical representation showing correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep and interpersonal adequacy.	129
4.42	Graphical representation showing correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep and communication skill.	130
4.43	Graphical representation showing correlation between withdrawal and personal adequacy.	133
4.44	Graphical representation showing correlation between withdrawal and interpersonal adequacy.	133
4.45	Graphical representation showing correlation between withdrawal and communication skill.	134

List of Images

Image Number	Title	Page Number
1.1	People recording videos instead of enjoying the moment	1
1.2	ABCD Personality Types	4
1.3	Surrounded by People using their phones	9
3.1	Division of the total sample	53

Abstract

This study explores the effect of Personality type (A/B) and Gender on Smartphone Addiction and Social Competence of Young Adults in India. Personality refers to the enduring characteristics and behavior that comprise a person's unique adjustment to life, including major traits, interests, drives, values, self-concept, abilities, and emotional patterns. Smartphone addiction, also known as "nomophobia," is often driven by excessive internet use or internet addiction disorder. It is not the device itself that triggers the compulsion, but rather the games, apps, and online platforms it provides unfettered access to. Social competence is effectiveness or skill in interpersonal relations and social situations, increasingly considered an important component of mental health. The study assesses the relationship between Smartphone Addiction levels and Social Competence with a sample size of 120 Individuals of age 18-24. Data was collected using the Type A/B Behavior Pattern Scale by Dr Upinder Dhar, Dr Santosh Dhar and Dr Manish Jain, Smartphone Addiction Scale by Dr Vijayshri and Dr Masaud Ansari & Social Competence Scale by Dr Latika Sharma and Dr Punita Rani. A strong negative correlation was found between smartphone addiction and social competence. A significant correlation was found between all the variables of smartphone addiction (compulsion, forgetfulness, lack of attention, depression and anxiety, disturbed hunger/sleep and social withdrawal) and social competence. (personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills)

Key Words: Personality Type, Gender, Smartphone Addiction, Social Competence and Young Adult.

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

Been to a college fest, a concert, a picnic, a cricket match or to celebrate new year's Eve? We find people constantly using their smartphones for photos and videos in a rush to capture the moment on their phones which they may not even go through again. But what we forget is to enjoy the present moment with oneself, family and friends and to interact with them. Do all of us do this?

(Stilwell, 2023)

Image 1.1 – People recording videos instead of enjoying the moment

1.1 Personality

Personality, as a psychological concept, encompasses the unique and consistent patterns of thinking, feeling, and behaving that individuals possess. Personality refers to the enduring characteristics and behavior that comprise a person's unique adjustment to life, including major traits, interests, drives, values,

self-concept, abilities, and emotional patterns (**American Psychological Association [APA]**). It encompasses various aspects such as moods, attitudes, opinions, and behavioral characteristics, both inherent and acquired. These characteristics distinguish one person from another and are most evident in their interactions with others. Personality can be observed in how individuals relate to their environment and social groups. The term personality has two main meanings in the field of psychology. The first meaning focuses on the consistent differences that exist between individuals, aiming to classify and explain stable psychological characteristics. The second meaning emphasizes the qualities that are common to all individuals and distinguish humans from other species. The study of personality originated from the recognition that individuals exhibit distinct patterns of behavior, such as their mannerisms, speech, living arrangements, and expression of desires.

Psychoanalytic Theory (1923), developed by Sigmund Freud, suggests that personality is composed of three components: the id, ego, and superego. The id represents our primal impulses and desires, while the ego acts as a mediator between the id and reality. The superego encompasses our moral standards and societal norms. According to this theory, personality is shaped by the interplay between these three elements. **Allport's Trait Theory (1937)** proposes that personality is the dynamic organization of psychophysical systems within an individual, which determine their unique adjustments to the environment. This theory emphasizes the individual's internal characteristics and how they interact with their surroundings. It suggests that personality is not fixed but rather influenced by various traits that remain relatively stable over time. **Trait Theory (1949)**, proposed by Gordon Allport, Raymond Cattell, and Hans Eysenck, posits that personality is composed of broad dispositions known as traits. These traits are relatively stable over time and have a significant

influence on our behaviours. This theory focuses on identifying and categorizing these traits to understand and predict individual personality differences. **Humanistic Theory (1961)**, proposed by Carl Rogers and Abraham Maslow, views personality as the outcome of choice, creativity, and self-actualization within an individual. It emphasizes the innate drive to realize and express one's full potential. This theory highlights the importance of personal growth, autonomy, and the pursuit of individual goals in shaping personality. **Social Cognitive Theory (1977)**, developed by Albert Bandura, suggests that personality is influenced by internal cognitive variables that shape our perception of the social environment. It emphasizes the constant interaction between our behaviours, thoughts, and the external world. This theory highlights the role of observational learning, self-efficacy, and the impact of social influences on personality development. **The Five-Factor Model (1990s)**, developed by Paul Costa and Robert McCrae, summarizes personality in terms of five broad factors: neuroticism, extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness. This model suggests that these factors encompass the fundamental dimensions of personality and can be used to describe and compare individuals. It provides a comprehensive framework for understanding personality traits and their impact on behaviour.

The Myers-Briggs Personality Type Indicator is a widely used self-report inventory that aims to determine an individual's personality type, strengths, and preferences. Developed by Isabel Myers and Katherine Briggs, the questionnaire is based on Carl Jung's theory of personality types. Today, the MBTI inventory is recognized as one of the most extensively utilized psychological instruments globally. By analyzing the responses provided in the inventory, individuals are categorized into one of the 16 personality types, namely: Extraversion (E) – Introversion (I), Sensing

(S) – Intuition (N), Thinking (T) – Feeling (F) and Judging (J) – Perceiving (P) The primary objective of the MBTI is to enable respondents to understand their personalities, their likes, dislikes, strengths, weaknesses, career preferences etc.

(Kendra Cherry,2023)

ABCD Personality Type was first introduced by cardiologists Meyer Friedman and Ray Rosenman in the 1950s. It initially included Type A and Type B types but has since been expanded to include types C and D. It categorizes individuals into four distinct personality types based on their behavior, attitudes, and responses to stress.

Personality Type A vs Type B vs Type C vs Type D						
	vs		vs		vs	
Type A		Type B		Type C		Type D
Stressful		Easy Going		Cautious/ Worried		Distressed
Workaholic		Procrastinator		Hard Working		Always working
Short Tempered		Fun loving		Serious		Depressed
Energetic		Laidback		Careful		Anxious
Ambition oriented		Balanced		Logics oriented		Routine oriented
Pessimistic		Optimistic		Deep thinker		Pessimistic
Competitive		Non-competitive		Perfectionist		Overly cautious

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The Pleasant Personality

(Mukherjee, 2023)

Image 1.2 – ABCD Personality Types

TYPE A

Type A individuals have a strong aversion to being constrained or limited by rules and regulations. Instead, they prefer to operate autonomously and establish their own timetables. Due to their tendency to be workaholics, it is not uncommon to witness their unwavering commitment and dedication towards achieving their

objectives. Occasionally, they may exhibit impatience, particularly when they perceive others as excessively fixated on minutiae or hindering their progress. It is not surprising to find individuals with this personality type in positions of supervision or management. With an inherent entrepreneurial spirit, they may either be business owners or aspire to become one in the future. Type A personalities exude confidence and are not easily disheartened.

Type A personality dimensions:

Tenseness - Type A personalities tend to be very tense and find it difficult to relax. They may clench their jaws or grind their teeth.

Impatience - Type A personalities feel impatient very frequently - when waiting in lines, when waiting on others to finish talking, and when wanting things to be done quickly.

Restlessness - They often tap their feet, can't sit still very long, and always feel like they should be getting things done. Type As exhibits a lot of restless behavior.

Achievement orientation - Extremely focused on achievement and attaining goals. Very competitive even in non-competitive situations. Set very high-performance standards.

Workaholic - Put excessive hours into work beyond what is really needed and often to the detriment of relationships and health. Struggle to ever feel like they are "off work" mode.

TYPE B:

Type B personalities have a strong inclination towards discussing themselves, which may be perceived as self-centeredness by some individuals. However, the underlying motivation for this behavior is the desire to be liked. To illustrate this point, consider the character Bette Midler portrays in the movie *Beaches*. In one scene, she invites an old friend to her opulent apartment and proceeds to share stories of her remarkable success. Yet, she quickly shifts the focus by saying, "Enough about me. Let's talk about you. So, what do you think of me?" This exemplifies the Type B personality's genuine aspiration to be well-regarded. Nevertheless, their greatest apprehension lies in the prospect of public humiliation, as it has the potential to garner disapproval from others. Such an experience can be deeply distressing for individuals with a Type B disposition. Consequently, they strive to conceal any vulnerabilities, aiming to present themselves as attractive and accomplished individuals.

Type B personality dimensions:

Complacent - Type B personalities tend to be satisfied with the status quo and content with their level of achievement. They do not push themselves for more.

Easy-going - They have a very laidback, easy-going attitude towards life compared to the urgency felt by Type A persons. Type Bs are calm.

Non-assertive - These individuals are typically less aggressive about putting themselves forward and expressing their agenda or needs. They are more passive.

Relaxed - As opposed to the tenseness of Type A's, Type B people are able to relax more easily and do so more often without guilt.

Patient - Exhibiting patience rather than irritation when encountering delays or slower pace is part of the Type B temperament.

There has been extensive research on the development of Type A traits- which states the role of nature and nurture both. It was found that Type A behaviour can be seen even in children aged 3 years, thus indicating hereditary factor of Type A personality trait. Studies on twins who have more or less similar genetic endowment also show difference in both Type A and Type B personality traits. By providing these twins different environment it is possible that both develop different personality traits as well. Several theorists suggests the role of parents- if parents have Type A personality, because of their behaviour, children would model that behaviour thus tend to become Type A personality. This was also suggested by Dr. Karen Matthews from university of Pittsburgh, parallels between Type A adults and Type A children. Type A children like their parents have high aspirations, try to complete tasks assigned on time and they would strive to achieve the highest. It may also develop as a result of child rearing practices where parents and strangers motivate children to achieve for higher levels.

TYPE C And TYPE D:

Type C individuals are those who place a high emphasis on attention to detail and give importance to logical and rational thinking when it comes to decision-making. They have analytical and objective traits, relying heavily on research and factual information rather than making decisions based on emotional opinions.

On the other hand, Type D personalities adopt a more cautious and deliberate approach in both their professional and personal lives. They value security and longevity, finding solace in following established routines. Unlike

their more outgoing counterparts, Type D individuals tend to shy away from social interactions and prefer to keep to themselves. Additionally, they exhibit a dislike for change and are more comfortable in stable environments. **(ABCD personality types: Characteristics of the four types,2024)**

1.2 What is Smartphone Addiction?

Smartphone addiction, also known as "nomophobia," is often driven by excessive internet use or internet addiction disorder. It is not the device itself that triggers the compulsion, but rather the games, apps, and online platforms it provides unfettered access to. This addiction can manifest in various impulse-control issues, such as prioritizing virtual relationships and online interactions over real-life, offline connections. People may become so engrossed in social networking, dating apps, texting, messaging and commenting that they neglect their in-person relationships and face-to-face interactions. It is not uncommon nowadays to witness couples or groups of friends sitting together in a restaurant or cafe, yet remaining mentally absorbed in their smartphones rather than conversing.

In 2016, about 70% of smartphone users in India were male, and 30% were female. In 2020, the split changed to 60% of male smartphone users and 40% of female smartphone users. According to a survey conducted in 2019, the highest penetration rate in the use of smartphones was for the age group of 18 to 24 years, with 37%. The next age group that uses smartphones the most is the age group of 24 to 35 years. **(Vardhman, 2024)**

Image 1.3 – Surrounded by People using their phones

While the internet and smartphone apps can undoubtedly facilitate new connections, these online-only relationships should not completely replace genuine human interactions, empathy and intimacy. Online friendships may seem more straightforward and convenient as they exist in a controlled digital environment, free from the nuances, challenges and effort required to sustain real-world relationships. However, excessive use of dating apps and platforms can shift one's focus towards false promises and scams.

Moreover, compulsive web surfing, video watching, gaming, and constant news feed checking can lead people to feel more isolated and disconnected. Excessive internet and smartphone use often cause individuals to neglect other important areas of their lives, including real-world relationships, hobbies, self-care, and social activities. The prioritization of likes, comments and online validation over real-life fulfilment impacts mental and emotional wellbeing. Additionally, compulsive smartphone use puts people at higher risk of addiction to online pornography as well.

Signs and Symptoms of Smartphone Addiction

Excessive phone usage can become problematic when it starts to consume a significant portion of your time, causing you to neglect important aspects of your life such as personal relationships, work, education, and hobbies. If you find yourself prioritizing reading social media updates over spending time with friends, or compulsively checking your phone while driving or during important lectures, it is crucial to re-evaluate your smartphone usage and strive for a healthier balance in your life.

There are several warning signs that indicate an addiction or overuse problem with smartphones or the internet. One such sign is difficulty in completing tasks at work or home, where you may find yourself neglecting household chores or professional responsibilities due to excessive online chatting, texting, or gaming. Additionally, excessive phone use can lead to isolation from family and friends, as the time spent on your device takes away from meaningful interactions. This can manifest in situations where you lose track of conversations or receive concerns from loved ones about the amount of time you spend on your phone. Concealing your smartphone use or lying about the extent of your online activities is another warning sign, as it suggests a sense of guilt or shame associated with your phone usage. Lastly, a "fear of missing out" (FOMO) can drive compulsive checking of social media platforms, stemming from the anxiety of feeling left out or not being up-to-date with important information. It is important to recognize these warning signs and take steps towards establishing a healthier relationship with your phone. Dimensions of smartphone addiction includes:

1. The phenomenon of **compulsion** in relation to smartphone addiction involves experiencing an irresistible urge to repeatedly check one's smartphone for notifications, messages, and other updates. This behavior becomes ingrained and habitual, resembling a ritual that is difficult to break free from.
2. **Forgetfulness** is another psychological phenomenon associated with smartphone addiction, wherein individuals become so engrossed or distracted by their smartphones that they forget to perform everyday tasks or fulfil their responsibilities. The constant presence of the smartphone can lead to a lack of focus on important matters.
3. **Lack of attention** is a common consequence of smartphone addiction, as individuals struggle to concentrate on tasks without being drawn to their smartphones to scroll through social media or check for updates. This behavior results in a shortened attention span and an inability to fully engage in activities that require sustained focus.
4. Excessive smartphone use has been found to have a correlation with **feelings of depression** and anxiety, and in some cases, it can exacerbate these mental health conditions. The relationship between smartphone use and depression and anxiety is likely bidirectional, with one influencing the other.
5. The use of smartphones before bedtime can **disrupt sleep** patterns, making it harder to fall asleep and stay asleep. The bright lights emitted by smartphones interfere with the body's natural circadian rhythms, leading to disturbed sleep. Additionally, the compulsion to check the phone during the night can result in sleep deprivation.

6. Another behavioral disruption caused by smartphone addiction is **disturbed hunger**. When individuals compulsively use their phones during meals, they may overeat or undereat without being aware of their body's natural appetite cues. This can have negative effects on overall health and well-being.

7. Spending excessive amounts of time alone on a smartphone can lead to **social withdrawal** and a diminished interest in real-world social interaction. The constant engagement with the virtual world can isolate individuals and hinder their ability to form and maintain meaningful relationships.

Chronic phone use can also cause physical dysfunctions - The brain's reward circuits can be chemically altered by chronic phone overuse, leading to dysfunction in the neurotransmitter gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA). GABA is an inhibitory neurotransmitter that has a calming and euphoric effect, as well as the ability to regulate fear and anxiety. This dysfunction in GABA plays a significant role in addiction by reinforcing substance use and addictive behaviors. Studies have shown that chronic phone use can disrupt the production of GABA, either increasing or decreasing its levels. Disturbances in the GABA system have been identified as a warning sign of addiction. In a research conducted by the Radiological Society of North America, it was found that heavy phone use was associated with an imbalanced ratio of GABA to other neurotransmitters. However, when teenagers with phone addiction received cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) for their disorder, their brain chemistry returned to a non-addicted ratio. Another consequence of chronic phone addiction is a decrease in grey matter in the brain. Grey matter is responsible for functions such as movement control, memory, and emotions (**Zhou, et. al, 2011**). Recent studies have used brain scans to examine individuals with phone addiction and

have discovered changes in the structure of their grey matter. The researchers noted that the physical shape and size of their brains resembled those of individuals with substance use disorders. Specifically, critical areas of grey matter volume were diminished in people addicted to their phones, similar to what is observed in individuals with substance use disorders.

A question that arises is that what is the relationship between social competence and smartphone addiction, So we can think of a situation where in a person who has high smartphone addiction, is always using his phone and doesn't talk with anyone face to face, his social competence will be very low, he will not be able to handle or initiate fruitful conversations with people and will lack basic communication skills required to present oneself in a social situation.

1.3 Social Competence

APA defines social competence as - effectiveness or skill in interpersonal relations and social situations, increasingly considered an important component of mental health. Social competence involves the ability to evaluate social situations and determine what is expected or required; to recognize the feelings and intentions of others; and to select social behaviours that are most appropriate for that given context. It is important to note, however, that what is required and appropriate for effective social functioning is likely to vary across settings (**APA Dictionary of Psychology, 2018**). It means how well a person is able to carry conversations in social situations or to maintain a close relationship with others, social competence includes different abilities related to personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy and communication skills. (***Social competence, 2024***)

1. **Personal adequacy** encompasses an individual's self-assurance, self-awareness, and confidence in their own capabilities. Those who possess a high level of personal adequacy exude a sense of competence in their identity and their potential for achievement.
2. **Interpersonal adequacy** pertains to an individual's proficiency in interacting with others. Individuals with high interpersonal adequacy possess the ability to cultivate positive relationships, demonstrate empathy towards others, and collaborate effectively within groups. They exhibit strong social skills.
3. **Communication skills** encompass an individual's aptitude to effectively exchange information through various means such as speaking, writing, listening, and nonverbal communication. Proficient communication skills entail the ability to articulate ideas and concepts clearly, actively engage in listening and comprehending others, and adapt communication strategies according to the specific context or situation.

The study of social competence originated in the early 20th century, with initial research focusing on how children interacted with their peers and functioned in social situations. In the 1930s, researchers began exploring the influence of children's characteristics on their positions within peer groups. Subsequently, in the 1950s and 1960s, studies established a link between children's social competence and their future mental health and academic performance. As evidence accumulated, the significance of social interactions became increasingly apparent, leading to a broader investigation of social competence. During this period, social competence was conceptualized in terms of problem-solving skills and effective social functioning. In the 1970s and 1980s, research shifted towards examining the impact of children's behavior on

relationships, which in turn influenced the study of teaching age, gender, and context-specific social skills. To understand the reasons behind some children's lack of social skills in specific interactions, researchers developed well-structured social information processing models. These models focused on various factors, including behavior, perception, evaluation, and the processing of social cues. They also explored the selection of social goals, decision-making processes, and the implementation of chosen responses. Additionally, studies during this time often investigated the correlation between social cognition and social competence. Notably, Frank Gresham emerged as a prominent researcher in the mid-1980s, identifying three sub-domains of social competence: adaptive behavior, social skills, and peer acceptance. Research during this period often concentrated on children who exhibited deficits in social skills, aiming to identify and provide assistance to these individuals. A commonly used framework for comprehending social competence is the social information-processing model by Crick and Dodge in 1994, delves into the cognitive processes that underlie the selection, enactment, and evaluation of responses. This model, likened to a computer metaphor, presents a nonlinear six-step process with feedback loops that connect children's social cognition and behavior. Any difficulties encountered at any of these steps typically result in deficits in social competence. The steps encompass the observation and encoding of relevant stimuli, including both non-verbal and verbal social cues, the interpretation and mental representation of these cues, the clarification of goals for the interaction, the development of a situation representation by accessing long-term memory or constructing it, the decision and selection of a response, and finally, the behavioral enactment and evaluation of the chosen response.

A different way to conceptualize social competence is by examining three underlying subcomponents within a hierarchical framework. At the top of the hierarchy lies social adjustment, which refers to the extent to which an individual attains society's developmentally appropriate goals. These goals encompass various aspects such as health, legal, academic, occupational, socioeconomic, social, emotional, familial, and relational statuses. Moving down the hierarchy, we find social performance, which assesses the degree to which an individual's responses to relevant social situations align with socially accepted criteria. Finally, at the lowest level, we have social skills, which encompass specific abilities like overt behavior, social cognitive skills, and emotional regulation that enable proficient performance in social tasks. This tri-component model proves valuable for medical professionals and researchers seeking to understand, predict, or enhance the social functioning of children.

Diana Rathjan (1980) identified several criteria for social competence, including social power, social relations, social skills, social mobility, social attraction, communicability, and social participation. For individuals, particularly students, the ability to interact effectively with peers and adults is crucial for their development and future outcomes as adults.

The extent to which an individual has acquired social competence plays a significant role in their success within society. Social competence encompasses the necessary skills and behaviors, both social, emotional, and cognitive, that are essential for successful interpersonal interactions and self-realization.

Socially competent individuals possess certain key attributes, such as knowledge and understanding of social rules, norms and roles within their relevant cultural contexts. They also have the ability to accurately interpret and understand others' subtle

behaviors, emotions and intentions during interactions. Socially competent people exhibit consistent, situationally appropriate reactions and responses to others' emotions, behaviors and social cues. Their habits, intentions and needs are aligned thoughtfully with those of the people around them. They project confidence during social interactions, while also demonstrating the willingness to accept vulnerability and potential rejection.

Ultimately, the most important outcomes of social competence are acceptance within relevant peer groups, the establishment of reciprocal friendships, and the ability to initiate and maintain positive relationships. As students develop social competence, they gain access to social resources, support and opportunities that can profoundly impact their development, wellbeing and success later in life. The societal implications are also significant, as a socially competent population facilitates cohesion, collaboration and harmony between diverse groups within communities and organizations. Thus the cultivation of social, emotional and cognitive abilities should be prioritized to equip individuals and societies to thrive.

Chapter 2

Review of Literature

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Depression, anxiety, and smartphone addiction in university students: A cross-sectional study.

The study delved into smartphone addiction among Lebanese university students, exploring links with depression, anxiety, and various factors.

Surveying 688 undergraduates, it found high rates of issues like compulsive behaviour and sleep disturbances linked to late-night smartphone use.

Surprisingly, gender, residence, academics, and certain habits showed no correlation. However, personality type A, younger age at first use, excessive weekday entertainment use, and experiencing depression or anxiety were associated with higher addiction scores. Even after considering other factors, depression and anxiety emerged as significant predictors of smartphone addiction. Ultimately, the findings underscored the impact of depression and anxiety, especially among stressed young adults lacking effective stress coping mechanisms, contributing to smartphone addiction.

2. Disconnect to detox: A study of smartphone addiction among young adults in India.

The study surveyed 240 Indian college students (18-25 years old) to explore smartphone addiction. About 25% showed high addiction scores, mainly spending time on apps like WhatsApp. Fear of missing out drove problematic usage, impacting sleep quality. The study emphasizes the need for digital detox and suggests curbing excessive smartphone use to avoid negative consequences among young adults in India.

3. Study of smartphone addiction: prevalence, pattern of use, and personality dimensions among medical students from rural region of central India.

This study investigated smartphone addiction among 146 medical students in Sawangi, India. They found a 24.65% prevalence of smartphone addiction, with a higher risk among females. Addiction was linked to the duration and frequency of smartphone use, as well as specific functions. Personality traits like assertiveness, depression, and emotional stability were associated with addiction and predicted it alongside usage duration. The study emphasizes the need for preventive measures and awareness campaigns to address harmful smartphone use among medical undergraduates in rural India.

4. Wu, Y. Y., & Chou, W. H. (2023). Smartphone addiction, gender and interpersonal attachment: A cross-sectional analytical survey in Taiwan.

This research investigates the connection between smartphone addiction, gender, and interpersonal attachment among Taiwanese individuals. A total of 1190 valid questionnaires were collected, consisting of 534 males and 656 females. The analysis of descriptive statistics reveals four distinct patterns of interpersonal attachment, namely secure, avoidant, dismissing, and anxious. The correlation analysis, using Spearman's ρ , demonstrates a significant positive correlation between smartphone addiction and interpersonal attachment ($p > 0.000$). However, no relationship is found between gender and either smartphone addiction or interpersonal attachment. The participants are categorized into high, moderate, and low addiction groups. The Analysis of

Variance (ANOVA) reveals statistically significant differences in the high and moderate addiction groups, but not in the low addiction group ($p < 0.204$).

These findings indicate that individuals with higher levels of smartphone addiction tend to experience insecurity in their interpersonal relationships. It highlights the importance of nurturing healthy interpersonal connections to address unhealthy smartphone addiction behaviors.

5. Chen, B., Liu, F., Ding, S., Ying, X., Wang, L., & Wen, Y. (2017). Gender differences in factors associated with smartphone addiction: A cross-sectional study among medical college students. BMC Psychiatry

A study was conducted in 2016 at Wannan Medical College in China to examine smartphone addiction among 1441 undergraduate students. The research used the Smartphone Addiction Scale short version (SAS-SV) to determine addiction levels. The study found that 29.8% of students were addicted to smartphones, with similar rates among male and female students. The study also discovered that different factors contribute to smartphone addiction based on gender. For male students, addiction was linked to the use of gaming apps, anxiety levels, and poor sleep quality. On the other hand, female students showed associations with the use of multimedia applications, social networking services, depression, anxiety, and poor sleep quality. These findings emphasize the importance of implementing interventions to address smartphone addiction among medical college students. It is crucial to develop gender-specific strategies to tackle the various factors that influence addiction. By recognizing these differences, targeted approaches can be implemented to effectively reduce smartphone addiction among students.

6. Behera, R. K., & Seth, M. K. (2023). Smartphone addiction among university students: Difference in gender and academic streams.

This research aims to explore the extent and factors contributing to smartphone addiction among university students, with a specific focus on gender and academic streams. A descriptive survey method was employed, and a total of 110 participants were selected using stratified random sampling. The data collection utilized the Smartphone Addiction Scale developed by Dr. Vijayshree and Dr. Masaud Ansari in 2020. The findings indicate that more than 40% of students exhibit signs of smartphone addiction, with 11% classified as highly addicted. While gender did not emerge as a significant predictor, academic streams showed a significant association with smartphone addiction. The t-test revealed no significant difference in addiction between male and female students, whereas the F-test highlighted a significant difference among students from different academic streams. Additionally, the two-way ANOVA demonstrated a significant interaction effect of gender and academic streams on smartphone addiction.

7. Sharma, M., & Singh, A. (2019). Gender Differences in Smartphone Addiction: Its Impact on Emotional Awareness.

This study investigates the impact of smartphone addiction on emotional awareness among Indian adolescents, focusing on gender differences. With smartphones becoming integral to the lives of youth in India, the study aims to understand how addiction to these devices affects emotional well-being. A sample of 300 students, randomly selected from Bathinda and Mansa,

participated in the study. Utilizing the Smartphone Addiction Scale (Kwon et al., 2013) and Emotion Awareness Questionnaire (Rieffe C et al., 2007), the research hypothesized that girls would demonstrate higher levels of smartphone addiction compared to boys and that those with lower addiction levels would exhibit better emotional awareness. Findings reveal a significant gender difference in smartphone addiction, with girls scoring higher ($M=157.30$, $SD=11.06$) than boys ($M=151.66$, $SD=12.07$) according to a T-test ($t=2.434^*$). However, the analysis of variance did not support the hypothesis regarding emotional awareness. Interestingly, a significant main effect of gender on emotional awareness emerged ($F=15.122^{**}$, $p<0.01$), highlighting the influence of gender on emotional awareness among adolescents, irrespective of smartphone addiction levels.

8. Davey, A., Nasser, K., & Davey, S. (2020). Gender Differential for Smartphone Addiction and its Predictors among Adolescents: Assessing Relationship with Self-Control via SEM Approach.

This research delves into the disparities in smartphone addiction predictors among teenagers, specifically examining the correlation with self-discipline. The objective is to uncover the elements that contribute to the growing issue of smartphone reliance among the youth. By utilizing Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to analyze data from 400 students in two CBSE schools in Meerut, the study sheds light on the gender-specific trends in smartphone addiction. The results indicate that male students are more inclined towards phubbing, with 53% exhibiting this behavior, in contrast to only 25% of female students. On the other hand, internet addiction appears to be more

prevalent among female students, with 48% reporting such tendencies compared to 33% of male students. Moreover, the study reveals that levels of self-control are significantly higher among male students, standing at 35%, as opposed to 25% among female students. These findings underscore the importance of understanding gender differences in smartphone addiction patterns and highlight the crucial role of self-control in managing addictive behaviors among adolescents. By recognizing these distinctions, interventions and strategies can be tailored to address the specific needs of male and female students, ultimately aiding in the prevention and reduction of smartphone addiction among the youth.

9. **Pradeep, B. S., Shenoy, A. B., Shahane, S., Srividya, R. N., Arelingaiah, M., D'Souza, R., Garady, L., Jyoti, M. K., Rache, S., Dixit, A., Yekkar, G. S., Lingaiah, P., Rajneesh, S., & Gururaj, G. (2022). Age, gender, peers, life skills and quality of life influence risk of cell phone addiction among college teachers in Karnataka, India: a state level epidemiological analysis.**

This research at the state level in Karnataka, India, delves into the reasons behind cell phone addiction among college teachers enrolled in the Life Skills Training and Counselling Services program. The study, which involved 1981 participants, focused on various factors like age, gender, peers, life skills, and quality of life to understand addiction risk. The results indicated that gender, number of peers, and social quality of life were connected to a higher risk of cell phone addiction. On the other hand, factors such as age, empathy, communication skills, and physical quality of life were found to be associated

with a lower risk of addiction. The study sheds light on how these socio-demographic factors and personal characteristics play a role in influencing cell phone addiction among college teachers. With the prevalence of cell phones in today's society, understanding these influences is crucial in addressing and preventing addiction. By examining the intricate relationship between these variables, the research provides valuable insights into the complex nature of cell phone addiction. It underscores the importance of considering a wide range of factors when studying addiction behaviors and highlights the need for targeted interventions to help individuals, especially college teachers, manage their cell phone use effectively. The findings of this study contribute to the growing body of knowledge on addiction and pave the way for further research in this area.

10. Pal, S., & Misra, K. S. (2019). Study of Social Competence with Reference to Gender.

This study explores the social skills of high school students, specifically looking at 48 boys and 48 girls from grades 10 and 12. The research used the Social Competence Inventory (SCI) created by K.S. Misra to evaluate 23 aspects of social competence. Gender differences in social skills were analyzed using the t-test. The main goal was to see if there were differences in social skills between male and female students. The findings revealed that male students scored higher in "Ethical Orientation" and "Futuristic Orientation" than their female counterparts. This suggests that boys may have a stronger sense of ethics and a more forward-thinking mindset compared to girls. The results provide insight into how gender can influence social

competence levels among high school students. Overall, this research sheds light on the social competence of male and female high school students. By using the SCI and conducting statistical analysis, the study was able to identify specific areas where gender differences in social skills exist. Understanding these variations can help educators and policymakers develop targeted interventions to support the social development of all students, regardless of gender.

11. Ahirrao, K. D. (2023). Gender Differences in Social Skill.

This research aims to explore the social skills of teenagers, with a specific focus on male (200) and female (241) students aged 15 to 18 years in junior college. The data was collected using the Social Competence Scale (SCS) developed by Sharma and Punita, using an incidental sampling method. The study compares various research variables between male and female students, with a particular emphasis on examining gender differences in social skills. To evaluate these differences, 't' scores and significance levels were calculated. The findings reveal that there is no significant disparity between genders in terms of interpersonal adequacy, communication skills, and overall social skills. However, there were variations observed in personal adequacy among adolescents based on their gender.

12. Hetmańczyk, H. H. (2015). Gender and Social Competence of Younger Students.

The research explored how boys and girls in early elementary school demonstrate social competence differently. It looked at four main aspects:

motivation to learn, antisocial actions, shyness, and ability to socialize. Information was gathered from the "Student Behavior Sheet," focusing on the section created by B. Markowska. The study included 36 third-grade students, with 53% being boys and 47% being girls. By examining the various factors that contribute to social competence, the study aimed to understand how gender influences these behaviors in young students. The data collected from the students' behavior sheets provided valuable insights into their learning motivation, social inhibitions, and interactions with peers. The sample group consisted of a relatively equal number of boys and girls, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of gender-specific expressions of social competence. Overall, the study shed light on the differences in how boys and girls exhibit social competence in the early stages of their education. By focusing on key factors such as antisocial behavior and socialization, researchers gained a deeper understanding of the unique challenges and strengths that each gender may face in social situations. The findings from this study contribute to the existing knowledge on gender-specific expressions of social competence among young students.

13. Condry, J.C.(1984). Gender identity and social competence.

This research delves into how individuals form their gender identity by looking at how they adopt society's ideas of what it means to be masculine or feminine, and how this impacts their ability to interact socially. The study identifies three key phases in the development of gender identity: becoming aware of one's gender, understanding one's gender orientation, and finally, solidifying one's gender identity. Each phase is explained in terms of how it

relates to a person's social growth. The study also examines how these stages of gender identity formation can influence a person's overall social competence. By exploring how individuals navigate through the process of understanding and embracing their gender identity, researchers can gain insights into how this impacts their ability to engage with others in social settings. This research also considers how these findings align with Bem's theory of androgyny, which suggests that individuals who possess both masculine and feminine traits may have an advantage in terms of social adaptability. Overall, this study sheds light on the intricate process of gender identity development and its connection to social competence. By breaking down the stages of gender identity formation and examining their implications on social interactions, researchers can better understand how individuals perceive themselves in relation to societal norms of masculinity and femininity. This research contributes to the ongoing conversation surrounding gender identity and provides valuable insights into how individuals navigate their sense of self within the context of social relationships.

14. Rahaman, M. M. (2017). A Study of Social Competence of Male and Female Pupils at Secondary Level in Malda District of West Bengal.

The research focused on examining the social skills of 392 high school students in the Malda District of West Bengal. The participants, consisting of 198 males and 194 females, were chosen through incidental sampling. To gather data, the researchers used the Social Competence Scale (SCS) created by Sharma, Shukla, and Shukla in 1992. The study employed t-test statistical methods to analyze the hypotheses. The findings indicated a notable contrast

in social competence levels between male and female students. Interestingly, the results showed that female students exhibited higher levels of social competence in comparison to their male counterparts. This suggests that there may be gender differences in how social skills are developed and displayed among adolescents in the region. Overall, the study shed light on the social competence of secondary-level pupils in the Malda District. By utilizing the SCS and statistical analysis, the researchers were able to identify gender-based variations in social skills. These results contribute to the existing knowledge on social competence and may have implications for educational practices and interventions aimed at enhancing social skills among students.

15. Yunjing Su, Zhonglian Yan, Wenqi Lin & Xuelin Liu (2024) The Relationship Between Smartphone Addiction and the Interpersonal Competence of Chinese Private College Students: A Moderated Mediation Model

Social skills play a crucial role in effective communication and maintaining relationships. In today's digital age, where smartphones are prevalent, understanding how social skills impact smartphone usage is important. This study focuses on exploring the connection between social skills and perceived smartphone usage, including positive and negative aspects such as smartphone addiction. The research involved 509 adult participants, and the data was analyzed using Pearson's product moment correlation and multiple regression analysis. The results revealed a significant link between social skills and both positive smartphone usage and smartphone addiction. Notably, social expressivity and emotional control were identified as key factors influencing

both positive smartphone usage and smartphone addiction. These findings emphasize the significance of social skills in guiding individuals towards healthy smartphone habits. By recognizing the impact of social skills on smartphone usage, researchers can further investigate ways to promote responsible and effective smartphone use. This study provides valuable insights for future research in this field, highlighting the importance of social skills in navigating the digital landscape.

16. Yunjing Su, Zhonglian Yan, Wenqi Lin & Xuelin Liu (2024) The Relationship Between Smartphone Addiction and the Interpersonal Competence of Chinese Private College Students: A Moderated Mediation Model

Interpersonal competence (IC) is extremely important for private college students in China as it affects their ability to socialize and succeed in employment. In order to understand this relationship better, a study was conducted to investigate the impact of smartphone addiction (SPA) on IC among Chinese private college students. The study also examined the role of negative emotions (NE) as a mediator and psychological resilience (PR) as a moderator. The sample consisted of 5473 Chinese private college students, with a majority being male and from urban households. The findings of the study revealed that SPA had a positive influence on IC, and this relationship was partially mediated by NE. Furthermore, PR played a moderating role in the relationships between SPA and NE, NE and IC, as well as SPA and IC. These findings provide valuable insights to improve the socialization and employment competitiveness of Chinese private college students.

17. Abd Rahim, N. A., Siah, Y. H., Tee, X. Y., & Siah, P. C. (2020).**Smartphone Addiction: Its Relationships to Personality Traits and Types of Smartphone Use.**

Studies have shown that personality traits, such as extroversion and introversion, play a significant role in smartphone addiction among users. However, the results regarding the connection between extroversion/introversion and smartphone addiction have been inconsistent, possibly due to differences in the types of smartphone activities. This research aims to investigate the relationships between extroversion/introversion, smartphone addiction, and the various types of smartphone use, as well as the potential mediating role of these activities in the extroversion/introversion-smartphone addiction link. A group of 318 undergraduate participants were selected for this study through purposive sampling. The findings indicate that both introverts and extroverts are associated with smartphone addiction. Interestingly, introverts tend to engage more in process-based activities on their smartphones, while extroverts are inclined towards social interactions. Moreover, the study revealed that process-based activities, rather than social uses, were positively correlated with smartphone addiction. Furthermore, the research discovered that process-based smartphone activities acted as a mediator in the relationship between introversion and smartphone addiction. These results suggest that intervention programs could be developed to provide alternative activities, especially for introverts, to decrease smartphone reliance and fulfill their process-oriented needs. By understanding the role of personality traits and types of smartphone use in addiction, strategies can be implemented to promote healthier smartphone habits among users.

18. Kheradmand, A., Amirlatifi, E., & Rahbar, Z. (2023). Personality traits of university students with smartphone addiction.

The prevalence of smartphone addiction has become a topic of concern due to the rapid increase in smartphone usage. This study aimed to examine the relationship between smartphone addiction and personality traits among university students. A total of 382 students from Tehran universities participated in the study and completed questionnaires related to smartphone addiction and personality traits. The results of the study revealed that 28.8% of the participants were identified as being prone to smartphone addiction. When comparing individuals with smartphone addiction to those without addiction, significant differences were found in certain personality traits. Those with addiction showed higher scores in novelty-seeking, harm avoidance, and self-transcendence, indicating a tendency towards narcissistic personality traits. On the other hand, individuals with smartphone addiction exhibited lower scores in persistence and self-directedness, which were also statistically significant. Although not statistically significant, it was observed that those with addiction tended to have higher levels of reward dependence and lower levels of cooperativeness. These findings suggest that certain personality traits, such as high novelty-seeking and low persistence, may contribute to the development of smartphone addiction.

19. Hosseinzadeh Siboni, F., Emami Sigaroudi, A., Pouralizadeh, M., & Maroufizadeh, S. (2023). Social Competence and Its Related Factors in High School Students: A Cross-sectional Study.

Social skills are very important for teenagers to have good relationships with others. A study in Rasht City, Iran, looked at how high school students' social skills were related to different factors. They found that most students were girls, first-born in their families, and had normal sleep patterns. The majority also lived with their parents. The average social skills score was good, and it was linked to factors like school grades, internet use, and sleep duration. The study showed that students with higher grades tended to have better social skills. On the other hand, being a girl, being the second child, having insomnia, and parents' divorce were linked to lower social skills. The researchers used different statistical methods to analyze the data, such as ANOVA and regression analysis. These methods helped them understand how different factors influenced students' social competence. In conclusion, the study highlighted the importance of social competence in high school students. It showed that factors like academic performance, gender, birth order, and family situation can affect teenagers' ability to interact with others. By understanding these factors, educators and parents can help students develop better social skills and build successful relationships in school and society.

20. Markiewicz, K., Kaczmarek, B. L. J., & Filipiak, S. (2021). Mediating Effect of Emotional and Social Competences on Interrelations Between Gender, Age and the Broad Autism Phenotype.

The main objective of this study was to examine how emotional intelligence and social competences influence the connection between gender, age, and the broad autism phenotype (BAP). The study involved 85 parents of children diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). These parents completed

questionnaires related to the Autism-Spectrum Quotient, emotional intelligence, and social competence. The findings revealed that emotional intelligence, specifically its dimensions associated with the ability to acknowledge and express emotions and to empathize, played a significant role in mediating the relationship between gender and BAP. Furthermore, certain aspects of social competences, such as behavior effectiveness in intimate and social situations, were also identified as important mediators. However, the study did not establish a confirmed link between age and BAP.

21. Zubair, A., Kamal, A., & Artemeva, V. (2018). Gender Differences in Character Strengths, Social Competence, and Peer Relations Among Pakistani and Russian University Students.

Zubair, Kamal, and Artemeva (2018) conducted a study to explore the variations in character strengths, social competence, and peer relations among 558 university students from Pakistan and Russia. The participants included both men and women aged 20 to 29 years. The researchers employed assessment protocols from the Brief Strength Test (Peterson, 2004), Social Competence Scale (Shahzad, 2001), and Index of Peer Relations (Hudson, 1996) to evaluate the key aspects. The findings revealed that character strengths and social competence had a positive influence on peer relations in both Pakistani and Russian samples. Moreover, gender played a significant role in moderating the relationship between character strengths and peer relations. Interestingly, women exhibited more character strengths than men in both samples. Pakistani women demonstrated better social competence than men, while no notable gender differences were observed in the Russian

sample. Conversely, Pakistani and Russian men displayed stronger peer relations compared to women. Cross-cultural comparisons indicated that Russian students scored higher in justice, temperance, transcendence, and social competence compared to their Pakistani counterparts. However, there were no significant cultural differences in wisdom, courage, humanity, and peer relations. This study provides valuable insights into the complex interplay of gender, cultural, and individual factors in character strengths, social competence, and peer relations among university students in Pakistan and Russia.

22. Jyoti, & Devi, S. (2022). Study of Social Competence in Relation to Self Esteem Among School Students.

Jyoti, a PhD research scholar, and Sharmila Devi, an Assistant Professor from Punjabi University, Patiala, conducted a study on the connection between social competence and self-esteem in senior secondary school students. They pointed out that education is a continuous process influenced by one's immediate environment, impacting not only career success but also social adaptation. Social competence, crucial for human growth, involves recognizing one's own needs and those of others, contributing to the welfare of society. In today's society, where self-involvement is prevalent, meaningful social connections are essential for personal development and happiness. The study suggested that social competence could improve qualities like self-assurance, drive, teamwork, conflict resolution, and self-esteem in children as they grow. The results indicated that there were no significant differences based on gender in the levels of social competence and self-esteem among

senior secondary school students. Furthermore, the study found a positive and notable link between social competence and self-esteem in this group of students. This research provides valuable insights into the relationship between social competence and self-esteem, underscoring their importance for the overall growth and well-being of adolescents.

23. Mroczek, B., Kotwas, A., Karpeta-Pawlak, I. E., Wolińska, W., & et al.

(2017). Relationships Between the Level of Social Competence and Work-related Behaviors in A Group of Physicians, Nurses, and Paramedics.

Bożena Mroczek, Artur Kotwas, Iwona Ewa Karpeta-Pawlak, and Weronika Wolińska, researchers from Pomeranian Medical University and Wrocław Medical University in Poland, conducted a study to explore the connection between social competence and work-related behaviors among physicians, nurses, and paramedics. The study took place from 2015 to 2016 and involved 432 medical professionals, including physicians (29.7%), nurses (36.96%), and paramedics (33.3%), with an average age of 38.00. These participants worked in various healthcare settings, such as hospitals (38.9%), primary care centers (6.9%), and emergency ambulance services (18.3%). By utilizing the Social Competence Questionnaire (SCQ) and the Work-Related Behaviour and Experience Patterns AVEM questionnaire, the researchers aimed to analyze the relationship between social competence and burnout syndrome, while considering sociodemographic factors. The results indicated that a quarter of the medical workers displayed symptoms of burnout syndrome, with Type G behavior patterns being the most prevalent (31.8%, $p < 0.0001$). The study also found that paramedics often exhibited Type G and Type S

behaviors, physicians displayed Type A and Type B behaviors, and nurses exhibited Type B and Type G behaviors. The researchers concluded that burnout syndrome is a significant concern among healthcare professionals and emphasized the need for comprehensive therapeutic and preventive measures. They also highlighted the importance of competence in situations requiring assertiveness, as well as in intimate and social exposure situations, in protecting medical workers against burnout syndrome.

24. Kennedy, Ralph., Aurora, I., Ramos, Nunez. (2021). Understanding the Link Between Social Skills and Phone Use.

Kennedy Ralph and Aurora I. Ramos Nunez from the College of Coastal Georgia conducted a study on Emotional Intelligence (EI), mindfulness, social competence, and problematic phone usage across different age groups. The research, published in the Journal of Student Research, aimed to explore how these factors relate to phone use behavior in individuals of varying ages. The hypothesis proposed that those with higher EI, social skills, and mindfulness would have lower scores on the Problematic Phone Usage Scale. The study involved 105 participants aged 18-30, 30 participants aged 31-40, 30 participants aged 41-50, and 21 participants aged 51 and older. Various survey instruments were utilized, including the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire-Short Form (TEIQ-SF), Kentucky Inventory of Mindfulness Skills, Social Competence, and Problematic Phone Usage Scale. Results showed a negative correlation between age and phone use, with older individuals demonstrating reduced phone usage. Furthermore, the findings revealed that younger adults had lower scores in EI, mindfulness, and social

competence compared to middle-aged and older adults. They also exhibited a higher level of problematic phone use. This study sheds light on the importance of emotional intelligence, mindfulness, and social skills in understanding and potentially reducing problematic phone usage, especially among different age groups.

25. Nitya, Krishna., Dolar, Doshi., Suhas, Kulkarni., Madupu, Padma, Reddy., Adepu, Srilatha., D, Satyanarayana. (2021). Does smartphone addiction affect social interaction: a study among dental students in Hyderabad.

A recent research study conducted by Nitya Krishna, Dolar Doshi, Suhas Kulkarni, Madupu Padma Reddy, Adepu Srilatha, and D Satyanarayana focused on the effects of smartphone addiction on social interaction anxiety in undergraduate dental students in Hyderabad. The study, published in the *International Journal of Adolescent Medicine and Health*, aimed to explore how the excessive use of smartphones impacts students' social abilities. By using the Smartphone Addiction Proneness Scale (SAPS-15) and the Social Interaction Anxiety Scale (SIAS), the researchers surveyed students from five dental institutions in Hyderabad. The results of the study, which involved 470 male and 1060 female participants, indicated that female students and those in their third year of study showed a higher likelihood of experiencing social interaction anxiety. Through the use of multiple logistic regression analysis, the researchers were able to confirm their hypothesis that smartphone addiction plays a role in influencing social interaction anxiety among undergraduate dental students. This highlights the potential consequences of

excessive smartphone use on the development of interpersonal communication skills. The study sheds light on the negative impact of smartphone addiction on social interaction anxiety among undergraduate dental students. With the easy accessibility of smartphones, students are more prone to addictive behaviors that can hinder their social interactions. By identifying the correlation between smartphone addiction and social anxiety, the researchers have emphasized the importance of addressing this issue to promote healthy communication skills among students. The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the effects of technology on social behavior and the need for interventions to mitigate the adverse consequences of smartphone addiction.

**26. Sunhee, Lee., Hye-Jin, Kim., Han-Gyo, Choi., Yang, Sook, Yoo. (2018).
Smartphone Addiction and Interpersonal Competence of Nursing**

Students.

Sunhee Lee, Hye-Jin Kim, Han-Gyo Choi, and Yang Sook Yoo conducted a study on smartphone addiction and interpersonal competence among nursing students. The research, published in the Iranian Journal of Public Health, aimed to investigate how different aspects of smartphone addiction and social support impact the interpersonal skills of nursing students. The study involved 324 college students from Catholic University in Seoul, Korea, who completed a questionnaire on smartphone addiction, social support, interpersonal competence, and general characteristics. The researchers used path analysis to analyze the relationships between smartphone addiction subscales, social support, and interpersonal competence. The results showed that the

cyberspace-oriented relationship, a specific aspect of smartphone addiction, and social support were positively correlated with the interpersonal competence of nursing students. The coefficients for these relationships were 1.360 ($P = 0.004$) and 0.555 ($P < 0.001$), respectively. However, other subscales of smartphone addiction did not show significant associations with interpersonal competence among nursing students. These findings highlight the need for effective smartphone teaching methods to improve the motivation and interpersonal skills of nursing students. By understanding the impact of smartphone addiction and social support on interpersonal competence, educators and healthcare professionals can develop strategies to help students navigate the challenges of excessive smartphone use and enhance their communication skills. Further research in this area could provide valuable insights for promoting healthy smartphone habits among nursing students.

27. Young-Sook, Kwon., Kyung, Shin, Paek. (2016). The Influence of Smartphone Addiction on Depression and Communication Competence among College Students.

A study by Young-Sook Kwon and Kyung Shin Paek, published in the *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, explored the connection between depression, communication skills, and smartphone addiction in college students. The goal was to pinpoint factors contributing to smartphone addiction in this group. The research involved 293 undergraduates who completed a survey from August 28 to September 15, 2015. The results indicated that 14.7% of the participants were at risk of smartphone addiction. The study revealed a positive correlation between depression and smartphone

addiction, suggesting that higher levels of depression were linked to increased smartphone dependency. On the other hand, communication competence was negatively associated with smartphone addiction, indicating that better communication skills were linked to lower levels of smartphone addiction. Further analysis identified depression, communication skills, daily smartphone usage time, grade, academic performance, and gender as significant predictors of smartphone addiction among college students. These findings highlight the importance of implementing interventions to reduce depression among students in order to prevent smartphone addiction.

28. Hee, Min, Kim., Sung, Hee, Shin. (2015). Comparison of Gender Factors Affecting Middle School Students' Smartphone Addiction.

In a recent study published in the *Journal of Korean Academy of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing*, researchers Hee Min Kim and Sung Hee Shin aimed to compare the factors that contribute to smartphone addiction in middle school boys and girls. The study involved 390 middle school students from Seoul, with 198 boys and 192 girls. The data collected was analyzed using the SPSS 20.0 program. The results revealed that boys' smartphone addiction was influenced by factors such as stress, using smartphones for ostentation and fashion, depression, self-control, and teacher control over smartphone use. On the other hand, girls' smartphone addiction was influenced by stress and the motivation to use smartphones for ostentation and fashion. These findings highlight the importance of considering gender differences when developing effective management programs to address smartphone addiction in middle school students.

29. Eun, Jee, Lee., Yune, Kyong, Kim., Su, Jin, Lim. (2017). Factors**Influencing Smartphone Addiction in Adolescents.**

In a recent study published in the Journal of Korean Academy of Child Health Nursing, researchers Eun Jee Lee, Yune Kyong Kim, and Su Jin Lim aimed to explore the factors that contribute to smartphone addiction in teenagers. They conducted a cross-sectional study involving 183 middle school students from 3 different schools. Data was collected through self-report questionnaires between April and May of 2017. To analyze the data, the researchers used various statistical methods including χ^2 test, Fisher's exact test, t-test, one-way ANOVA, correlation coefficient analysis, and binary logistic regression with SPSS Ver. 21.0. The results of the study showed that the average score for smartphone addiction was 29.40, and approximately 21.3% of the adolescents were classified as being at risk for smartphone addiction. Through logistic regression analysis, the researchers identified several significant factors associated with the risk of smartphone addiction. These factors included gender, school life, smartphone usage time, and parental control. Interestingly, the study concluded that school satisfaction played a crucial role in determining the likelihood of smartphone addiction among adolescents. Additionally, the findings suggested that a control-oriented approach by parents in managing their children's smartphone use did not reduce the risk of addiction and may have even worsened it. The authors emphasized the importance of further research to better understand how teachers and parents can effectively manage teenagers' smartphone usage.

30. Liron, Ben-Yehuda., Liel, Greenberg., Aviv, Weinstein. (2016). Internet Addiction by Using the Smartphone-Relationships between Internet Addiction, Frequency of Smartphone Use and the State of Mind of Male and Female Students.

The study conducted by Liron Ben-Yehuda, Liel Greenberg, and Aviv Weinstein explored the connections between Smartphone usage, Internet addiction, and users' level of interest. The researchers aimed to analyze how often individuals used their Smartphones in various situations, such as when they were bored, engaged in passive activities, or involved in active activities. By doing so, they hoped to gain insights into the potential impacts of Smartphone use on individuals' physical, mental, and behavioral well-being. The authors of the study focused on investigating the correlation between Smartphone use, Internet addiction, and the level of interest among users. They specifically examined the differences in the frequency of Smartphone usage in different scenarios, including moments of boredom, passive engagement, and active participation. The primary objective of this research was to uncover the potential effects of Smartphone use on individuals' physiological, psychological, and behavioral aspects. Unfortunately, the abstract of the study does not provide any specific details or findings. To gain a comprehensive understanding of the research, one would need to refer to the full article, which would offer more in-depth information about the research methodology, results, and conclusions drawn by the authors

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction:

An appropriate research methodology provides a proper direction and path to the researcher on the way of research. It is a way through which we can know how to solve research problems systematically and scientifically.

The chapter includes objectives of the study, hypothesis to be tested. It gives a detailed description of variables included research design, sample, and procedure of the research. It includes details about the dimensions and scoring of the standardized scales used in the research and lastly the statistical methods used for the analysis of data.

3.2 Title of the Study:

To Study the Impact of Personality Type and Gender on Smartphone Addiction and Social Competence of Young Adults.

3.3 Objectives:

1. To assess the relationship between smartphone addiction and social competence.
2. To examine the differences in the mean levels of social competence among participants with type A, type B, and type A-B personality.
3. To assess the differences in the mean levels of social competence between male and female participants.
4. To investigate the differences in the mean levels of smartphone addiction among participants with type A, type B, and type A-B personalities.

5. To examine the differences in the mean levels of smartphone addiction between male and female participants.
6. To assess the interaction effect of personality type and gender on the mean level of smartphone addiction.
7. To compare the mean scores of smartphone addiction among males of Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
8. To compare the mean scores of smartphone addiction among females of Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
9. To compare the mean scores of social competence among males of Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
10. To compare the mean scores of social competence among females of Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
11. To assess the differences in the mean scores of compulsion between males and females.
12. To examine the differences in the mean scores of forgetfulness between males and females.
13. To investigate the differences in the mean scores of lack of attention between males and females.
14. To assess the differences in the mean scores of depression & anxiety between males and females.
15. To examine the differences in the mean scores of disturbed hunger/sleep between males and females.

16. To investigate the differences in the mean scores of social withdrawal between males and females.
17. To assess the differences in the mean scores of personal adequacy between males and females.
18. To examine the differences in the mean scores of interpersonal adequacy between males and females.
19. To investigate the differences in the mean scores of communication skills between males and females.
20. To compare the mean scores of compulsion among Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
21. To compare the mean scores of forgetfulness among Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
22. To compare the mean scores of lack of attention among Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
23. To compare the mean scores of depression and anxiety among Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
24. To compare the mean scores of disturbed hunger/sleep among Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
25. To compare the mean scores of social withdrawal among Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
26. To compare the mean scores of personal adequacy among Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.

27. To compare the mean scores of interpersonal adequacy among Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
28. To compare the mean scores of communication skills among Type A, Type B, and Type A-B Personality.
29. To examine the correlation between compulsion and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
30. To assess the correlation between forgetfulness and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
31. To investigate the correlation between lack of attention and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
32. To examine the correlation between depression and anxiety and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
33. To assess the correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
34. To investigate the correlation between social withdrawal and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.

3.4 Null Hypothesis:

1. **H₀₁:** There is no significant correlation between smartphone addiction and social competence.
2. **H₀₂:** There is no significant difference in the mean level of social competence among participants with type A, type B and type A-B personality.

3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant difference in the mean level of social competence among male and female participants.
4. **H₀₄**: There is no significant difference in the mean level of smartphone Addiction among participants with type A, type B and type A-B personalities.
5. **H₀₅**: There is no significant difference in the mean level of smartphone Addiction among male and female participants.
6. **H₀₆**: There is no significant interaction effect of personality type and gender on the mean level of smartphone Addiction.
7. **H₀₇**: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of smartphone addiction among males of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
8. **H₀₈**: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of smartphone addiction among females of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
9. **H₀₉**: There is no significant difference in the means scores of social competence among males of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
10. **H₀₁₀**: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social competence among females of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
11. **H₀₁₁**: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of compulsion of males and females.
12. **H₀₁₂**: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of forgetfulness of males and females.
13. **H₀₁₃**: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of lack of attention of males and females.

14. **H₀14:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of depression & anxiety of males and females.

15. **H₀15:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of disturbed hunger/sleep of males and females.

16. **H₀16:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social withdrawal of males and females.

17. **H₀17:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of personal adequacy of males and females.

18. **H₀18:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of interpersonal adequacy of males and females.

19. **H₀19:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of communication skills of males and females.

20. **H₀20:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of compulsion among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

21. **H₀21:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of forgetfulness among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

22. **H₀22:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of lack of attention among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

23. **H₀23:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of depression and anxiety among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

24. **H₀24:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of disturbed hunger/sleep among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

25. **H₀25:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social withdrawal among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
26. **H₀26:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of personal adequacy among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
27. **H₀27:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of interpersonal adequacy among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
28. **H₀28:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of communication skills among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
29. **H₀29:** There is no significant correlation between compulsion and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
30. **H₀30:** There is no significant correlation between forgetfulness and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
31. **H₀31:** There is no significant correlation between lack of attention and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
32. **H₀32:** There is no significant correlation between depression and anxiety and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
33. **H₀33:** There is no significant correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
34. **H₀34:** There is no significant correlation between social withdrawal and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.

3.5 Variables:

The present research includes two independent variables, two dependent variables and four control variables. Following is the tabular representation of variables:

Table 3.1

The independent variables and the dependent variables of the study

Independent Variable (IV _A)	Personality Type
Independent Variable (IV _B)	Gender
Dependent Variable (DV ₁)	Smartphone Addiction
Dependent Variable (DV ₂)	Social Competence
Control Variables	Age- 18 to 24 Years Family Type – Nuclear Medium of Education - English Location- Urban Socio-Economic strata- Middle Class (including Upper Middle, Middle and Lower Middle Class)

3.6 Research Design:

Quantitative research was used with the help of Questionnaires. The design used is Within Subjects. To determine the impact of Gender and Personality type on Smartphone Addiction and Social Competence, two independent variables and two dependent variables were taken: first independent variable being Personality type divided into three levels- type A, type B and type A-B, second independent variable being Gender divided into two levels- male and female, two continuous dependent variable namely smartphone addiction and social competence. Thus two 3 X 2 factorial design is used for the study one for each dependent variable. Design for smartphone addiction as dependent variable is as following:

Table 3.2**Research Design of the study for Smartphone Addiction**

Personality Type(A)	Gender (B)	
	MALE (B1)	FEMALE (B2)
TYPE A (A1)	A1B1	A1B2
TYPE B (A2)	A2B1	A2B2
TYPE A-B (A3)	A3B1	A3B2

A1B1 in the table represents mean of smartphone addiction scores of male participants having type A personality, similarly A2B1 represents mean of smartphone addiction scores of male participants having type B personality and A3B1 represents mean of smartphone addiction scores of male participants having type A-B personality. A1B2 represents mean of smartphone addiction scores of female participants having type A personality, A2B2 indicates mean of smartphone addiction scores of female participants having type B personality and lastly A3B2 represents mean of smartphone addiction scores of female participants having Type A-B personality.

Design for social competence as second dependent variable will be as following:

Table 3.3**Research Design of the study for Social Competence**

Personality Type(A)	Gender (B)	
	MALE (B1)	FEMALE (B2)
TYPE A (A1)	A1B1	A1B2
TYPE B (A2)	A2B1	A2B2
TYPE A-B (A3)	A3B1	A3B2

A1B1 in the table represents mean of social competence scores of male participants having type A personality, similarly A2B1 represents mean of social competence scores of male participants having type B personality and A3B1 represents mean of social competence scores of male participants having type A-B personality. A1B2 represents mean of social competence scores of female participants having type A personality, A2B2 indicates mean of social competence scores of female participants having type B personality and lastly A3B2 represents mean of social competence scores of female participants having Type A-B personality.

3.7 Selection of Sample:

Convenience and Purposive Sampling Methods were used. Undergraduate and Postgraduate Students were⁴ selected from different colleges of Ahmedabad, keeping in mind the inclusion criteria for the research:

Inclusion Criteria-

- Ability and willingness to give informed consent
- Undergraduate and postgraduate students pursuing their degrees from any college or university in Ahmedabad
- Aged between 18 to 24 on the date of answering the survey
- Living in a Nuclear Family
- Should be from middle class (including upper middle class and lower middle class)
- Knowledge of English language in order to understand the questions of the survey

Exclusion Criteria-

- Students pursuing UG or PG degrees who don't fall in the age range of 18 to 24
- Students who are from colleges that aren't in the city of Ahmedabad
- People not from middle class family
- People living in Joint Families
- People who do not have an understanding of English language
- People who are not willing to give consent to participate
- Incomplete survey

The sample size of the study is 120 and is further divided into more groups:

Image 3.1 – Division of the total sample

3.8 Procedure:

In order to uphold the ethical standards of the research, prior permission was obtained from the Head of the Department of Psychology at St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Ahmedabad. Subsequently, an informed consent letter was created and

attached to the survey. This consent letter provided a comprehensive explanation of the research objectives, the criteria for participant inclusion, the ethical guidelines that would be followed throughout the study, and the rights of the participants. Following this, students from various colleges and universities were approached and provided with hardcopies of the survey forms. They were instructed to complete the forms in accordance with their own lifestyle and ideologies. Alongside the consent form, the participants were also required to provide their demographic details, which were relevant to the study. A total of 120 participants were sampled from various colleges in Ahmedabad. The data collected during the research was then entered into SPSS and analyzed accordingly.

3.9 Research Tools:

1. Type A/B Behavioural Pattern Scale

Developed by Dr Upinder Dhar, Dr Santosh Dhar and Dr Manish Jain. This scale consists of 33 items - 17 items for Form A divided into three dimensions – I Efficacious, II Tenseness, III. Zealous and 16 items for Form B divided into three dimensions - I Poised, II Complacent, III Non-Assertive. For Adults. The reliability of the scale was measured by split-half method on 200 participants and was found out to be 0.54 for Both Type A and Type B. Validity of the test is 0.73 for Type A and Type B both. A score is given to every sentence for both form A and from B which is as follows:

Table 3.4**Scoring for Type A/B Behavioural Pattern Scale**

Strongly Agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
5	4	3	2	1

Sum of the scores of Form A and Form B gives a total Type A score and Type B score respectively. The interpretation can be done by the norms table which is according to the dimensions for both Form A and Form B.

Dimension wise Norms for Interpretation of Raw Scores – Form A

Table 3.5**Dimensions of Form A**

Dimensions	1. Efficacious	2. Tenseness	3. Zealous	Total
High	38 and Above	17 and Above	21 and Above	62 and Above
Normal Range	29 – 37	10 – 16	14 - 20	46 – 61
Low	28 and Below	9 and Below	13 and Below	45 and Below
Items Statements	3,4,5,7,9,12,16,17	8,10,13,15	1,2,6,11,14	All
Total	08	04	05	17

Dimension wise Norms for Interpretation of Raw Scores – Form B

Table 3.6
Dimensions of Form B

Dimensions	1. Poised	2. Complacent	3. Non-Assertive	Total
High	39 and Above	15 and Above	10	61 and Above
Normal Range	29 – 38	8 – 14	6 - 9	46 – 60
Low	28 and Below	7 and Below	5 and Below	45 and Below
Items Statements	1,3,4,6,7,8,9,11,12,13	5,14,15,16	2,10	All
Total	10	04	02	16

2. The Smartphone Addiction Scale –

Developed by Dr Vijayshri and Dr Masaud Ansari. The scale includes 23 items divided into Six Dimensions— I. Compulsion, II. Forgetfulness, III. Lack of Attention, IV. Depression and Anxiety, V. Disturbed Hunger/Sleep, VI. Social Withdrawal. The test was developed by assessing students of age range-14-24 years. It is a Likert scale with alternatives namely: Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. Cronbrch’s Alpha was used to calculate reliability and was found out to be 0.857 at 0.01 significant level. Content validity and construct validity were used to know the validity of the test. The scoring is done as mentioned below:

Table 3.7**Scoring for Smartphone Addiction Scale**

Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
5	4	3	2	1

Sum of the scores are done to get a raw score which can be used to interpret the level

of smartphone addiction. The interpretations are done as follows:

Table 3.8**Interpretation of Smartphone Addiction Scale**

Raw Score	Grade	Level of Smartphone Addiction
88 and Above	A	Very High Level of Addiction
81 to 87	B	High Level of Addiction
66 to 80	C	Above Average Level of Addiction
51 to 65	D	Average Level of Addiction
40 to 50	E	Below Average Level of Addiction
29 to 39	F	Low Level of Addiction
28 and Below	G	Very Low Level of Addiction

3. Social Competence Scale

Developed by Dr Latika Sharma and Dr Punita Rani. This scale consists of 47 items divided into three competencies–I. Personal Adequacy, II. Interpersonal Adequacy, III. Communication Skills. It was standardized on 500 students of 16+ years of age. Test-retest and Split-half methods were used to calculate the reliability and it had +0.843 and 0.76 at 0.01 level of significance respectively. Content validity was used by approaching 10 subject experts and 200 items initially and then 47 items were finalized. The scoring for the positive and negative statements is done differently. (A sign of • means the statement is negative).

Table 3.9
Scoring for Social Competence Scale

Nature of Item	Always	Mostly	Sometime	Never
Positive	4	3	2	1
Negative	1	2	3	4

The level of Social Competence can be calculated by sum of all the scores and by following the norms table below:

Table 3.10
Interpretation of Social Competence Scale

Categories	Description	Ranges of Score
A	Very Good	168 – 188
B	Good	148 – 167
C	Average	108 – 147
D	Poor	78 – 107
E	Very Poor	47 - 77

3.10 Statistical Tools:

To fulfill the objectives of the research, the following statistical tools were used in accordance with the assumptions of each tool to analyze the collected data.

SPSS version 23 was used for the analysis of data.

Table 3.11
The Analysis of Data

Sr. No	Statistical Tools	Assessment of Items
1.	One-way ANOVA	The test was done to analyze the significant difference of smartphone addiction and social competence of males and females with respect to Personality type
2.	Two-way Independent Measures ANOVA	The test was done to analysis was done to study the impact of Personality Type and Gender on Smartphone Addiction
3.	Kruskal- Wallis Test	The test was done to analyze the significant difference of dimensions of smartphone addiction and social competence with respect to gender and personality type
4.	Spearman's Rank Correlation	The test was done to find the correlation between Smartphone Addiction and Social Competence and their dimensions.

Formulas

One Way-ANOVA

$$F = \frac{MSB}{MSW}$$

In the above-given formula,

F = coefficient of ANOVA.

MSB = Mean sum of squares between the groups.

MSW = Mean sum of squares within groups.

Spearman Correlation Co-efficient

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6\sum d_i^2}{n(n^2-1)}$$

In the above-given formula,

d_i = Distinction between each observation's two ranks

n = Numerical value for the number of observations.

ρ = Spearman's Rank Coefficient

Two Way-ANOVA

$$F_G = \frac{MSBG}{MSWG}$$

In the above-given formula, F = Coefficient of ANOVA.

MSBG = Mean sum of squares between the group of Gender.

MSWG = Mean sum of squares within group of Gender

$$F_P = \frac{MSBP}{MSWP}$$

In the above-given formula, F = Coefficient of ANOVA.

MSBP = Mean sum of squares between the group of Personality Type

MSWP = Mean sum of squares within group of Personality Type

$$F_{P \times G} = \frac{MSBP_{xG}}{MSWP_{xG}}$$

In the above-given formula, F = Coefficient of ANOVA.

MSB_{PxG} = Mean sum of squares between the group of interaction of Personality Type and Gender

MSW_{PxG} = Mean sum of squares within group of interaction of Personality Type and Gender

Kruskal-Wallis H test

$$H = \frac{12}{n(n+1)} \sum \frac{T_i^2}{n_i} - 3(n+1)$$

In the above given formula,

n_i = Sample size for a population

T_i = Rank sum for population

n = Total number of Observations

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between smartphone addiction and social competence.

Table 4.1

Summary of Correlation for Smartphone Addiction total and Social Competence Total

			SAT- SMARTPHONE ADDICTION TOTAL	SCT-SOCIAL COMPETENCE TOTAL
Spearman's rho	SAT- SMARTPHONE ADDICTION TOTAL	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2- tailed) N	1.000 . 120	-.600** .000 120
	SCT-SOCIAL COMPETENCE TOTAL	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2- tailed) N	-.600** .000 120	1.000 .000 120

**, Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Graph 4.1

Graphical representation showing correlation between smartphone addiction and social competence.

The correlation between Smartphone Addiction and Social Competence is illustrated in the table above, with the mean of smartphone addiction being 60.225 and the mean of social competence being 134.708. Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Social Competence. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.600, suggesting a Strong Negative correlation between Smartphone Addiction and Social Competence. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Smartphone Addiction and Social Competence is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject H_0

The strong negative correlation observed between smartphone addiction and social competence aligns with the findings of Mansuri and Mathur (2019), who

investigated the impact of internet addiction on social competence among adolescents. Their study revealed a lower level of social competence among adolescents with internet addiction compared to those without. This connection suggests a parallel in the detrimental effects of excessive screen time, whether through smartphones or the internet, on social abilities. The factors contributing to the negative correlation, such as excessive device usage detracting from face-to-face interactions, the preference for online communication, and the resultant social withdrawal and reduced self-esteem, echo the challenges identified in Mansuri and Mathur's study. Additionally, the hindrance of empathy and emotional intelligence, distractions during interactions, neglect of real-world activities, and the cyclical nature of addiction and social withdrawal further underline the complexities highlighted in both studies. Together, these findings and justifications paint a comprehensive picture of how technology addiction, whether through smartphones or the internet, can detrimentally impact social competence, highlighting the need for balanced technology use and the development of healthy social habits, especially among adolescents.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean level of social competence among participants with type A, type B and type A-B personality.

Table 4.2

Summary of comparison of means of social competence in context of personality type.

	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SCT-SOCIAL COMPETENCE TOTAL	TYPE A	38	53.20
	TYPE B	36	61.68
	TYPE A-B	46	65.61
	Total	120	

SCT-SOCIAL COMPETENCE TOTAL	
Kruskal-Wallis H	2.710
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.258

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: PERSONALITY TYPE

Graph 4.2

Graphical representation of comparison of means of social competence in context of personality type.

Table 4.2 shows the results of effect of personality types on social competence among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of social competence of Type A participants is 53.20, Type B participants is 61.68 and for Type A-B is 65.61. The associated p value here is 0.258, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.258 > 0.05$).

Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

This results suggests that the various characteristics that make up a person's personality are not fixed and can interact with each other, leading to different outcomes in different situations. Previous studies, such as the one conducted, have found a correlation between being outgoing and possessing good social abilities. This indicates that certain personality traits can contribute to an individual's social skills. However, the complexity of personality is not solely determined by inherent traits but is also influenced by external factors and experiences. As individuals grow older, their personality can undergo changes due to various influences in their environment. This could explain why individuals in the study exhibited similar levels of social skills, despite having different personality types. In essence, this suggests that personality is not a static construct but rather a dynamic and evolving aspect of an individual. It is influenced by a combination of inherent traits and external factors, leading to a complex interplay that can result in different outcomes in different situations.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean level of social competence among male and female participants.

Table 4.3

Summary of comparison of means of social competence in context of gender.

Ranks			
	GENDER	N	Mean Rank
SCT-SOCIAL COMPETENCE TOTAL	Male	60	62.43
	Female	60	58.57
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SCT-SOCIAL COMPETENCE TOTAL
Chi-Square	.371
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.542

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: GENDER

Graph 4.3

Graphical representation of comparison of means of social competence in context of gender.

Table 4.3 shows the results of effect of Gender on social competence among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of social competence of Male participants is 62.43, Female participants is 58.57. The associated p value here is 0.542, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.542 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

Social competence is not just about gender; it is affected by various factors. Gender roles and expectations related to communication and emotions are changing, which may result in similar social skills between males and females. Studies show that gender differences in social behavior have lessened over the years, supporting the results of this research. Additionally, cultural backgrounds, education, and personal traits all contribute to shaping social competence, regardless of gender. The idea that social skills are not solely determined by gender is supported by the evolving nature of traditional gender roles and societal norms. Research conducted by Rahaman (2017) gave contradictory results, showed that female students exhibited higher levels of social competence in comparison to their male counterparts. This suggests that there may be gender differences in how social skills are developed and displayed among adolescents in the region. Moreover, cultural influences, educational backgrounds, and individual characteristics all have significant impacts on the development of social competence, irrespective of gender.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference in the mean level of smartphone addiction among participants with type A, type B and type A-B personalities.

H₀₅: There is no significant difference in the mean level of smartphone Addiction among male and female participants.

H₀₆: There is no significant interaction effect of personality type and gender on the mean level of smartphone Addiction.

Table 4.4
Summary of Two-way ANOVA for Smartphone Addiction in context of
Personality Type and Gender.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	2287.916 ^a	5	457.583	1.521	.189
Intercept	421956.852	1	421956.852	1402.544	.000
PT	1377.508	2	688.754	2.289	.106
Gender	209.067	1	209.067	.695	.406
PT * Gender	492.703	2	246.352	.819	.444
Error	34297.009	114	300.851		
Total	471831.000	120			
Corrected Total	36584.925	119			

a. R Squared = .063 (Adjusted R Squared = .021)

Graph 4.4

Graphical representation of comparison of means of smartphone addiction in
context of Personality Type

Graph 4.5

Graphical representation of comparison of means of smartphone addiction in context of Gender.

Table 4.4 presents the findings of the study that examined the impact of Personality Type and Gender on Smartphone Addiction using Two-way Independent Measures ANOVA. The obtained p value for Personality Type is 0.106, which exceeds the predetermined alpha level of 0.05 ($0.106 > 0.05$). Consequently, we do not have sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis H_04 . Similarly, the calculated p value for Gender is 0.406, which is greater than the assigned alpha value of 0.05 ($0.406 > 0.05$). Hence, we fail to reject the null hypothesis H_05 . Furthermore, the associated p value for the interaction between Personality Type and Gender is 0.444, which also surpasses the predetermined alpha value of 0.05 ($0.444 > 0.05$). Therefore, we do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis H_06 .

The results of this study support the notion that personality types do not always directly link to smartphone addiction. Previous research conducted by Kheradmand and Amirlatifi (2023), comparing individuals with smartphone addiction to those without addiction, significant differences were found in certain personality traits. Those with addiction showed higher scores in novelty-seeking, harm avoidance, and self-transcendence, indicating a tendency towards narcissistic personality traits. On the other hand, individuals with smartphone addiction exhibited lower scores in persistence and self-directedness, which were also statistically significant. Although not statistically significant, it was observed that those with addiction tended to have higher levels of reward dependence and lower levels of cooperativeness. These findings suggest that certain personality traits, such as high novelty-seeking and low persistence, may contribute to the development of smartphone addiction.

By recognizing that various behaviors and characteristics can influence smartphone use, researchers and professionals can develop more comprehensive strategies to address and understand smartphone addiction in different individuals.

Previous studies conducted indicated that males could have higher rates of smartphone addiction. However, recent data suggests that the gender gap in technology usage habits is decreasing is shown in research by Wu, Y. Y., & Chou, W. H. (2023), a study of 1190 participants (534 males and 656 females) found there is no relationship between gender and smartphone addiction. Chen, B., Liu, F., Ding, S., Ying, X., Wang, L., & Wen, Y. (2017) found 29.8% of students were addicted to smartphones, with similar rates among male and female students. The study also discovered that different factors contribute to smartphone addiction based on gender. For male students, addiction was linked to the use of gaming apps, anxiety levels, and poor sleep quality. On the other hand, female students showed associations with the

use of multimedia applications, social networking services, depression, anxiety, and poor sleep quality. This shift may be due to the widespread availability of smartphones among all age groups and the evolving societal attitudes towards technology. The research underscores that gender should not be the sole factor in predicting smartphone addiction. It stresses the significance of examining individual behaviors and environments when assessing technology usage patterns. As technology continues to play a central role in daily life, understanding these nuances becomes crucial in addressing and preventing smartphone addiction.

Previous research that showed how personality traits such as neuroticism and impulsivity can impact smartphone addiction. However, studies also revealed that these effects do not differ significantly between males and females. The study emphasizes that although both personality traits and gender play a role in technology use, the specific interaction between the two may not be a major factor in predicting smartphone addiction. To summarize, the studies underscores the intricate and diverse nature of smartphone addiction, which is influenced by a combination of personality traits, gender, and individual behaviors. The findings suggest that while personality types, gender, and their interaction may have some impact on smartphone addiction, these factors alone may not be enough to accurately predict it.

H₀₇: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of smartphone addiction of males of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.5

Summary of Mean Scores of Smartphone Addiction among Males by Personality Type

ANOVA

SA- MALE

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	793.477	2	396.738	1.443	.245
Within Groups	15670.707	57	274.925		
Total	16464.183	59			

Descriptives

SA- MALE

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
TYPE A	16	62.63	14.836	3.709	54.72	70.53	30	83
TYPE B	21	60.00	19.962	4.356	50.91	69.09	23	89
TYPE A-B	23	53.96	14.140	2.948	47.84	60.07	30	79
Total	60	58.38	16.705	2.157	54.07	62.70	23	89

Graph 4.6

Graphical representation of comparison of means of smartphone addiction among males in context of Gender.

Table 4.5 shows the results of effect of Personality Type on Smartphone Addiction among Male participants, analysed using One Way ANOVA test. The associated p value here is 0.245, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.245 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

The results from this study support previous research that suggests personality traits can impact smartphone addiction differently based on gender. Abd Rahim, N. A., Siah, Y. H., Tee, X. Y., & Siah, P. C. (2020) findings indicate that both introverts and extroverts are associated with smartphone addiction. Interestingly, introverts tend to engage more in process-based activities on their smartphones, while extroverts are inclined towards social interactions. Moreover, the study revealed that process-based activities, rather than social uses, were positively correlated with smartphone addiction. Various intervention programs could be developed to provide alternative activities, especially for introverts, to decrease smartphone reliance and fulfill their process-oriented needs. This deeper understanding can provide valuable insights for developing interventions and prevention strategies tailored to different demographic groups. Ultimately, recognizing the diverse influences on smartphone addiction can help address the issue more effectively and promote healthier technology habits among individuals.

H₀₈: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of smartphone addiction among females of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.6

Summary of Mean Scores of Smartphone Addiction among Females by Personality Type

ANOVA

SA-FEMALE

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	51.530	2	25.765	.075	.928
Within Groups	19662.204	57	344.951		
Total	19713.733	59			

Descriptives

SA-FEMALE

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
TYPE A	16	62.31	18.384	4.596	52.52	72.11	35	103
TYPE B	21	63.10	20.290	4.428	53.86	72.33	28	94
TYPE A-B	23	60.96	17.001	3.545	53.60	68.31	35	92
Total	60	62.07	18.279	2.360	57.34	66.79	28	103

Graph 4.7

Graphical representation of comparison of means of smartphone addiction among females in context of Personality Type.

Table 4.6 shows the results of effect of Personality Type on Smartphone Addiction among Female participants, analysed using One Way ANOVA test. The associated p value here is 0.928, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.928 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

This suggests that factors beyond personality, such as social and environmental influences, play a crucial role in determining smartphone addiction among females. It is important to consider individual behaviors, social factors, and contextual elements when addressing smartphone addiction in females with different personality types. The lack of significant differences in addiction scores among females indicates that interventions for smartphone addiction should focus on broader

factors rather than just personality traits. By understanding the complexities of smartphone use and addiction in females, we can develop more effective strategies to promote healthy technology habits and combat excessive smartphone use.

H₀₉: There is no significant difference in the means scores of social competence among males of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.7

Summary of Mean Scores of Social Competence among Males by Personality Type

		Ranks	
	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SC-Male	TYPE A	16	26.41
	TYPE B	21	28.21
	TYPE A-B	23	35.43
	Total	60	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SC-Male
Chi-Square	3.079
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.215

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
PERSONALITY TYPE

Table 4.7 shows the results of effect of personality types on social competence among Male participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of social competence of Type A participants is 26.41, Type B participants is 28.21 and for Type A-B is 35.43. The associated p value here is 0.215, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.215 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H₀₉.

Graph 4.8

Graphical representation of comparison of means of social competence among males in context of Personality type.

The results of this study indicate that personality traits alone may not accurately predict social competence in males. Previous research conducted by Pal, S., & Misra, K. S. (2019) findings revealed that male students scored higher in "Ethical Orientation" and "Futuristic Orientation" than their female counterparts. This suggests that boys may have a stronger sense of ethics and a more forward-thinking mindset compared to girls. The results provide insight into how gender can influence social competence levels among high school students. The findings support the idea that social competence is influenced by a combination of personality traits, environmental factors, and personal experiences. By considering the multifaceted nature of personality and its interaction with social contexts, interventions and programs aimed at improving social skills in males can be tailored to address a wide range of individual needs and experiences. This study contributes to the growing body of research that highlights the complexity of social development and emphasizes the

need for comprehensive approaches to understanding and promoting social competence in males with diverse personality profiles

H₀₁₀: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social competence among females of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.8

Summary of Mean Scores of Social Competence among Females by Personality Type

Ranks			
	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SC-Female	TYPE A	16	31.00
	TYPE B	21	26.21
	TYPE A-B	23	34.07
	Total	60	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

SC-Female	
Kruskal-Wallis H	2.238
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.327

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: PERSONALITY TYPE

Table 4.8 shows the results of effect of Personality Type on Social Competence among Female participants, analysed using One Way ANOVA test. The associated p value here is 0.431, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.431 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H₀₁₀.

Graph 4.9

Graphical representation of comparison of means of social competence among females in context of Personality type.

Previous research has shown that personality types alone may not be strong indicators of social competence in females. Factors such as culture, family dynamics, and peer relationships play a significant role in shaping social competence among females.. The study emphasizes the importance of taking a comprehensive approach to understanding social behaviors in females. It indicates that social competence is influenced by a combination of personality traits, environmental factors, and individual experiences. Interventions and programs designed to improve social skills in females should consider this multifaceted nature of social development,tailoring strategies to meet diverse needs and contexts. By recognizing the complexities of the

relationship between personality types and social competence among females, this study provides valuable insights for promoting healthy social interactions effectively.

H₀₁₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Compulsion of males and females.

Table 4.9

Summary of Mean Scores of Compulsion by Gender

ANOVA

SA1-COMPULSION

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	42.008	1	42.008	1.334	.250
Within Groups	3716.583	118	31.496		
Total	3758.592	119			

Table 4.9 shows the results of effect of Gender on Compulsion scores among participants, analysed using One Way ANOVA test. The associated p value here is 0.250, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.250 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H₀₁₁.

The results obtained from this study indicate that gender alone may not serve as a strong predictor of compulsive tendencies. The absence of significant differences in compulsion scores between genders in this study emphasizes the need for a comprehensive approach when examining compulsive behaviors. Interventions and prevention strategies aimed at addressing compulsive tendencies should take into consideration individual differences, contextual factors, and the diverse manifestations of compulsive behaviors across genders. This study contributes to the broader understanding of compulsive behaviors by shedding light on their complexity

and variability across male and female populations, providing valuable insights for developing effective tailored approaches to address compulsive tendencies.

Graph 4.10

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Compulsion in context of Gender.

H₀12: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Forgetfulness of males and females.

Table 4.10

Summary of Mean Scores of Forgetfulness by Gender

Ranks			
	GENDER	N	Mean Rank
SA2-FORGETFULLNESS	Male	60	56.80
	Female	60	64.20
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SA2-FORGETFULNESS
Chi-Square	1.389
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.239

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
GENDER**Graph 4.11**

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Forgetfulness in context of Gender.

Table 4.10 shows the results of effect of Gender on Forgetfulness scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Forgetfulness of Male participants is 56.80, Female participants is 64.20. The associated p value here is 0.239, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.239 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0

Previous studies have indicated that forgetfulness is a common occurrence among people, regardless of their gender, and can be affected by various factors like stress, workload, and lifestyle. Additionally, societal norms and expectations regarding memory and forgetfulness may differ, but they do not necessarily result in significant gender disparities in forgetful behaviors.

H₀13: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of lack of attention of males and females.

Table 4.11

Summary of Mean Scores of Lack of Attention by Gender

Ranks			
	GENDER	N	Mean Rank
SA3-LACK OF ATTENTION	Male	60	55.13
	Female	60	65.88
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SA3-LACK OF ATTENTION
Chi-Square	2.923
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.087

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
GENDER

Table 4.11 shows the results of effect of Gender on Lack of Attention scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Lack of Attention of Male participants is 55.13, Female participants is 65.88. The associated p value here is 0.087, which is greater

than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.087 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_{013}

Graph 4.12
Graphical representation of comparison of means of Lack of Attention in context of Gender.

The results of this study indicate that there may not be a significant difference in the experience of lack of attention between males and females. People's ability to pay attention can vary greatly and can be affected by various factors like stress, cognitive load, and distractions in the environment.

H₀14: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Depression and Anxiety of males and females.

Table 4.12

Summary of Mean Scores of Depression & Anxiety by Gender

Ranks			
	GENDER	N	Mean Rank
SA4-DEPRESSION AND ANXIETY	Male	60	57.76
	Female	60	63.24
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SA4-DEPRESSION AND ANXIETY
Chi-Square	.751
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.386

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
GENDER

Graph 4.13

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Depression and Anxiety in context of Gender.

Table 4.12 shows the results of effect of Gender on Depression and Anxiety scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Depression and Anxiety of Male participants is 57.76, Female participants is 63.24. The associated p value here is 0.386, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.386 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 14.

This discovery indicates that the rates of depression and anxiety may not vary greatly between men and women. Depression and anxiety are common mental health issues that affect people of all genders and can be influenced by various factors like genetics, life events, and coping strategies. Moreover, societal norms and cultural beliefs regarding emotional expression may not lead to significant variations in reported levels of depression and anxiety between men and women.

H₀15: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of disturbed hunger/sleep of males and females.

Table 4.13

Summary of Mean Scores of Disturbed Hunger/Sleep by Gender

Ranks			
	GENDER	N	Mean Rank
SA5-DISTURBED HUNGER/SLEEP	Male	60	59.37
	Female	60	61.63
	Total	120	

Table 4.13 shows the results of effect of Gender on Disturbed Hunger/Sleep scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Disturbed Hunger/Sleep of Male participants is 59.37, Female participants is 61.63. The associated p value here is

0.720, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.720 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

Graph 4.14

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Disturbed Hunger/Sleep in context of Gender.

The research findings indicate that there is no substantial difference in the prevalence of disturbed hunger and sleep between men and women. Issues with sleep and appetite are common problems that can affect individuals of any gender, and are influenced by various factors like stress, lifestyle choices, and underlying health issues. This suggests that disturbances in hunger and sleep are more related to individual responses to stressors rather than inherent gender differences. It is important for interventions addressing disrupted eating and sleeping patterns to take into account these shared experiences and focus on universal approaches that cater to the individual needs of all individuals, regardless of gender.

H₀₁₆: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social withdrawal of males and females.

Table 4.14
Summary of Mean Scores of Social Withdrawal by Gender

Ranks			
	GENDER	N	Mean Rank
SA6-WITHDRAWAL	Male	60	60.43
	Female	60	60.58
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}	
	SA6-WITHDRAWAL
Chi-Square	.001
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.981

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
GENDER

Table 4.14 shows the results of effect of Gender on Social Withdrawal scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Social Withdrawal of Male participants is 60.43, Female participants is 60.58. The associated p value here is 0.981, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.981 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H₀₁₆

Graph 4.15

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Withdrawal in context of Gender.

The findings of this study indicate that there is no substantial variation in the prevalence of social withdrawal between men and women. Withdrawing from social interactions can be a typical reaction to stress, anxiety, or other psychological factors, regardless of whether someone is male or female. It is important to acknowledge that societal expectations and cultural norms can impact how individuals, regardless of gender, navigate social situations and may contribute to comparable patterns of social withdrawal.

H₀17: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of personal adequacy of males and females.

Table 4.15
Summary of Mean Scores of Personal Adequacy by Gender

Ranks			
	GENDER	N	Mean Rank
SC1-PERSONAL ADEQUACY	Male	60	61.14
	Female	60	59.86
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SC1-PERSONAL ADEQUACY
Chi-Square	.041
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.840

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
GENDER

Graph 4.16

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Personal Adequacy in context of Gender.

Table 4.15 shows the results of effect of Gender on Personal Adequacy scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Personal Adequacy of Male participants is 61.14, Female participants is 59.86. The associated p value here is 0.840, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.840 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

The results of this study indicate that there is no significant difference in the sense of personal adequacy between males and females. Factors like self-esteem, self-efficacy, and perceptions of one's abilities can influence feelings of personal adequacy, and these factors are not inherently tied to gender. Moreover, societal norms and cultural expectations surrounding personal achievements and success may not lead to significant differences in perceived personal adequacy between genders. The absence of notable variations in personal adequacy scores between males and females in this study highlights the shared experiences of feeling capable and competent across diverse populations. This result emphasizes the importance of interventions and strategies that consider universal approaches to enhance personal adequacy, catering to the individual needs of each person, regardless of gender. By recognizing personal adequacy as a common aspect of self-perception experienced by both males and females, interventions can focus on promoting positive self-talk, building confidence, and fostering a sense of accomplishment.

H₀18: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of interpersonal adequacy of males and females.

Table 4.16

Summary of Mean Scores of Interpersonal Adequacy by Gender

Ranks			
	GENDER	N	Mean Rank
SC2-INTERPERSONAL ADEQUACY	Male	60	63.54
	Female	60	57.46
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SC2-INTERPERSONAL ADEQUACY
Chi-Square	.920
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.337

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
GENDER

Graph 4.17

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Interpersonal Adequacy in context of Gender.

Table 4.16 shows the results of effect of Gender on Interpersonal Adequacy scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Interpersonal Adequacy of Male participants is 63.54, Female participants is 57.46. The associated p value here is 0.337, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.337 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

The results of this study indicate that there is no significant variation in the ability to navigate social interactions and relationships between males and females. Factors like communication skills, empathy, and the ability to establish meaningful connections can influence interpersonal adequacy, and these factors are not inherently linked to gender. Furthermore, societal expectations and cultural norms surrounding social interactions may not lead to significant differences in perceived interpersonal adequacy between genders. The absence of notable disparities in interpersonal adequacy scores between males and females in this study highlights the shared experiences of feeling competent in social situations across diverse populations. These findings imply that interventions and strategies aimed at improving interpersonal skills should adopt universal approaches that cater to the individual needs of each person, regardless of gender. By recognizing interpersonal adequacy as a common aspect of social functioning experienced by both males and females, interventions can focus on promoting effective communication, empathy, and the development of healthy relationship-building skills.

H₀19: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of communication skills of males and females.

Table 4.17

Summary of Mean Scores of Communication Skills by Gender

Ranks			
	GENDER	N	Mean Rank
SC3-COMMUNICATION SKILL	Male	60	61.12
	Female	60	59.88
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SC3-COMMUNICATION SKILL
Chi-Square	.038
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.846

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
GENDER

Graph 4.18

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Communication Skills in context of Gender.

Table 4.17 shows the results of effect of Gender on Communication Skill scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Communication Skills of Male participants is 61.12, Female participants is 59.88. The associated p value here is 0.846, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.846 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

The results of this study indicate that there is not a significant difference in the ability to effectively convey thoughts, ideas, and emotions between males and females. Factors such as upbringing, education, and personal experiences can influence communication skills, and these factors are not inherently tied to gender. It is important to note that societal expectations and cultural norms surrounding communication may not lead to significant differences in perceived communication skills between genders. The lack of significant differences in communication skills scores between males and females in this study highlights the shared experiences of feeling competent in conveying information and engaging in effective dialogue across diverse populations. Based on these findings, interventions and strategies aimed at enhancing communication abilities should take a universal approach that caters to the individual needs of each person, regardless of their gender. By recognizing communication skills as a common aspect of social interaction experienced by both males and females, interventions can focus on promoting active listening, assertiveness, and adaptability in communication styles.

H₀₂₀: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of compulsion among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.18
Summary of Mean Scores of Compulsion by Personality Type
Descriptives
 SA1-COMPULSION

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
TYPE A	38	21.47	5.270	.855	19.74	23.21	12	33
TYPE B	36	18.97	6.286	1.048	16.85	21.10	7	31
TYPE A-B	46	19.43	5.193	.766	17.89	20.98	9	33
Total	120	19.94	5.620	.513	18.93	20.96	7	33

ANOVA

SA1-COMPULSION					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	134.841	2	67.421	2.177	.118
Within Groups	3623.750	117	30.972		
Total	3758.592	119			

Table 4.18 shows the results of effect of personality types on Compulsion scores among participants, analysed using One-Way ANOVA. The associated p value

here is 0.118, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.118 > 0.05$).

Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

Graph 4.19
Graphical representation of comparison of means of Compulsion in context of Personality Type.

The research results indicate that the tendency towards repetitive and ritualistic behaviors, commonly linked to compulsions, may not vary significantly based on different personality types. Compulsive behaviors can be influenced by a variety of factors such as stress levels, coping strategies, and neurobiological aspects, which may not be directly associated with specific personality traits. Moreover, the overlap between Type A and Type B personalities, as observed in Type A-B, might contribute to the absence of significant differences in compulsive behaviors among these groups. The lack of notable variations in compulsion scores among individuals with Type A, Type B, and Type A-B personalities in this study highlights the intricate nature of compulsive behaviors and their potential universality across personality types. This outcome emphasizes the importance of tailored interventions and

strategies that address the specific triggers and underlying causes of compulsions, rather than solely focusing on personality classifications. By acknowledging compulsive behaviors as a shared aspect of human behavior, interventions can be tailored to address stress management, healthy coping mechanisms, and cognitive-behavioral techniques to alleviate the impact of compulsions.

H₀21: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of forgetfulness among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.19

Summary of Mean Scores of Forgetfulness by Personality Type

Ranks			
	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SA2-FORGETFULNESS	TYPE A	38	72.71
	TYPE B	36	59.49
	TYPE A-B	46	51.21
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SA2-FORGETFULNESS
Chi-Square	8.181
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.017

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
PERSONALITY TYPE

Table 4.19 shows the results of effect of personality types on Forgetfulness scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Forgetfulness of Type A participants is 72.71, Type B participants is 59.49 and for Type A-B is 51.21. The associated p

value here is 0.017, which is smaller than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.017 < 0.05$). Therefore, we reject the H_0 .

Graph 4.20
Graphical representation of comparison of means of Forgetfulness in context of Personality Type.

This results indicates that the likelihood of forgetfulness, which impacts memory recall and retention, may vary depending on different personality types. Previous studies have shown that forgetfulness can be influenced by factors like stress, attention span, and cognitive abilities, which can differ among various personality categories. Additionally, lifestyle factors like sleep quality, physical health, and daily routines can also impact forgetfulness, varying among individuals with different personality types.

H₀₂₂: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Lack of attention among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.20

Summary of Mean Scores of Lack of Attention by Personality Type

Ranks			
	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SA3-LACK OF ATTENTION	TYPE A	38	66.84
	TYPE B	36	60.57
	TYPE A-B	46	55.21
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SA3-LACK OF ATTENTION
Chi-Square	2.376
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.305

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
PERSONALITY TYPE

Graph 4.21

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Lack of Attention in context of Personality Type.

Table 4.20 shows the results of effect of personality types on Lack of Attention scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Lack of Attention of Type A participants is 66.84, Type B participants is 60.57 and for Type A-B is 55.21. The associated p value here is 0.305, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.305 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

The results indicate that variations in attention levels, affecting focus and task performance, may not be strongly linked to specific personality types. This could be due to the intricate relationship between attentional abilities and various contributing factors, regardless of personality traits. Attention can be influenced by external stimuli, cognitive functions, and differences in neural activity. This underscores the importance of considering a wide array of factors beyond personality categorizations when devising strategies to enhance attention and concentration.

H₀23: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of depression and anxiety among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.21

Summary of Mean Scores of Depression & Anxiety by Personality Type

Ranks			
	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SA4-DEPRESSION AND ANXIETY	TYPE A	38	70.13
	TYPE B	36	55.11
	TYPE A-B	46	56.76
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SA4- DEPRESSIO N AND ANXIETY
Chi-Square	4.339
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.114

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
PERSONALITY TYPE**Graph 4.22**

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Depression and Anxiety in context of Personality Type.

Table 4.21 shows the results of effect of personality types on Depression and Anxiety scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Depression and Anxiety of Type A participants is 70.13, Type B participants is 55.11 and for Type A-B is 56.76. The associated p value here is 0.114, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.114 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 23.

The results of this study suggest that the levels of depression and anxiety may not vary significantly based on different personality types. This could be due to the fact that depression and anxiety are complex conditions influenced by a combination of biological, psychological, and environmental factors. While personality traits may play a role in susceptibility to these conditions, they are not the sole determinants. However, factors such as stressors, coping strategies, and social support networks also contribute significantly to the development and severity of anxiety symptoms. Therefore, it is important to consider a holistic approach that takes into account various aspects of an individual's life when addressing depression and anxiety.

H₀₂₄: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of disturbed hunger/sleep among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.22

Summary of Mean Scores of Disturbed Hunger/Sleep by Personality Type

Ranks			
	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SA5-DISTURBED HUNGER/SLEEP	TYPE A	38	69.38
	TYPE B	36	57.03
	TYPE A-B	46	55.88
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SA5-DISTURBED HUNGER/SLEEP
Chi-Square	3.686
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.158

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
PERSONALITY TYPE

Graph 4.23

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Disturbed Hunger/Sleep in context of Personality Type.

Table 4.22 shows the results of effect of personality types on Disturbed Hunger/Sleep scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Disturbed Hunger/Sleep of Type A participants is 69.38, Type B participants is 57.03 and for Type A-B is 55.88. The associated p value here is 0.158, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.158 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

The results shows that disruptions in hunger and sleep, which can greatly impact overall well-being, may not differ significantly based on personality types. One possible reason for this finding is the close connection between sleep problems and personality traits. Certain personality traits may make individuals more prone to sleep issues, lifestyle choices, stress levels, and underlying health conditions also play important roles. However, factors like physical activity, caffeine consumption, and

mental health status were found to influence this relationship, highlighting the complexity of the issue.

H₀₂₅: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social withdrawal among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.23

Summary of Mean Scores of Social Withdrawal by Personality Type

		Ranks	
	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SA6-WITHDRAWAL	TYPE A	38	68.32
	TYPE B	36	59.93
	TYPE A-B	46	54.49
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SA6-WITHDRAWAL
Chi-Square	3.330
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.189

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
PERSONALITY TYPE

Table 4.23 shows the results of effect of personality types on Social Withdrawal scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank Social Withdrawal of Type A participants is 68.32, Type B participants is 59.93 and for Type A-B is 54.49. The associated p value here is 0.189, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.189 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H₀₂₅.

Graph 4.24

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Withdrawal in context of Personality Type.

The results suggest that the tendency to withdraw socially may not vary significantly based on personality types. This could be due to the various factors that contribute to social withdrawal, including personality traits, environmental influences, and personal experiences. Nevertheless, factors such as social support, coping mechanisms, and past experiences of rejection or acceptance also significantly impacted social behavior. The results emphasize the importance of considering both personality traits and external influences when addressing social withdrawal through interventions.

H₀26: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of personal adequacy among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.24

Summary of Mean Scores of Personal Adequacy by Personality Type

Ranks			
	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SC1-PERSONAL ADEQUACY	TYPE A	38	53.09
	TYPE B	36	59.49
	TYPE A-B	46	67.41
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SC1-PERSONAL ADEQUACY
Chi-Square	3.580
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.167

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
PERSONALITY TYPE

Graph 4.25

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Personal Adequacy in context of Personality Type.

Table 4.24 shows the results of effect of personality types on Personal Adequacy scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank Personal Adequacy of Type A participants is 53.09, Type B participants is 59.49 and for Type A-B is 67.41. The associated p value here is 0.167, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.167 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

The results suggest that self-esteem, self-worth, and confidence levels may not vary significantly based on personality types. This could be because personal adequacy is influenced by a combination of internal beliefs, self-perceptions, and external validation rather than just personality traits. Factors such as social support, life satisfaction, and perceived success also played important roles. This highlights the multifaceted nature of self-esteem and personal adequacy, showing that they are not solely determined by personality traits. Beliefs about one's abilities, accomplishments, and self-worth are more closely related to personal adequacy than specific personality traits. The study's findings emphasize the importance of considering individual beliefs and self-concept when addressing personal adequacy through interventions.

H₀27: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of interpersonal adequacy among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.25

Summary of Mean Scores of Interpersonal Adequacy by Personality Type

Ranks			
	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SC2-INTERPERSONAL ADEQUACY	TYPE A	38	56.68
	TYPE B	36	60.03
	TYPE A-B	46	64.02
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SC2-INTERPERSONAL ADEQUACY
Chi-Square	.938
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.626

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
PERSONALITY TYPE

Graph 4.26

Graphical representation of comparison of means of Interpersonal Adequacy in context of Personality Type.

Table 4.25 shows the results of effect of personality types on Interpersonal Adequacy scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank Interpersonal Adequacy of Type A participants is 56.68, Type B participants is 60.03 and for Type A-B is 64.02. The associated p value here is 0.626, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.626 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

The results of this study suggest that people's ability to interact socially and form relationships may not vary significantly based on their personality categorizations. This could be explained by the fact that interpersonal adequacy is influenced by various factors beyond just personality traits. Personality traits alone do not solely determine one's ability to interact socially and build relationships. The lack of significant differences in interpersonal adequacy scores among individuals with different personality types in this study emphasizes the idea that effective social interactions and relationship-building skills are not solely dependent on personality traits. Instead, they are influenced by a combination of personality, experiences, and learned behaviors. This study highlights the importance of interventions that go beyond personality-focused approaches and consider addressing individuals' beliefs about their social abilities, providing opportunities for skill-building, and creating supportive social environments. Strategies like social skills training, group therapy, and communication workshops can be beneficial for individuals in developing and improving their interpersonal skills, regardless of their personality categories.

H₀₂₈: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of communication skills among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

Table 4.26
Summary of Mean Scores of Communication Skills by Personality Type

Ranks			
	PERSONALITY TYPE	N	Mean Rank
SC3-COMMUNICATION SKILL	TYPE A	38	52.93
	TYPE B	36	66.97
	TYPE A-B	46	61.68
	Total	120	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SC3-COMMUNICATION SKILL
Chi-Square	3.108
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.211

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
 b. Grouping Variable:
 PERSONALITY TYPE

Graph 4.27
Graphical representation of comparison of means of Communication Skills in context of Personality Type.

Table 4.26 shows the results of effect of personality types on Communication skill scores among participants, analysed using Kruskal Wallis test, the non-parametric version of one-way ANOVA. The mean rank of Communication skills of Type A participants is 52.93, Type B participants is 66.97 and for Type A-B is 61.68. The associated p value here is 0.211, which is greater than the assigned alpha value, 0.05 ($0.211 > 0.05$). Therefore, we fail to reject the H_0 .

The results of this study indicate that personality types did not have a significant impact on how individuals perceive their communication abilities. This suggests that there are other factors at play that influence communication skills beyond just personality traits. Factors like upbringing, education, and workplace environment play a significant role in shaping an individual's communication skills. In conclusion, this study suggests that effective communication abilities are not solely determined by personality traits. Instead, they are influenced by a combination of personality, experiences, and learned behaviors. To improve communication skills, interventions should consider addressing multiple factors and utilize strategies like communication workshops, role-playing exercises, and feedback sessions. By recognizing the complexity of communication skills, individuals can be empowered to express themselves effectively and build strong interpersonal relationships.

H029: There is no significant correlation between compulsion and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.

Table 4.27

Summary of Correlation between Compulsion and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills

Correlations

	SA1-COMPULSION	SC1-PERSONAL ADEQUACY	SC2-INTERPERSONAL ADEQUACY	SC3-COMMUNICATION SKILL
Spearman's rho	1.000	-.439**	-.446**	-.382**
Correlation Coefficient				
Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000
N	120	120	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Graph 4.28

Graphical representation showing correlation between compulsion and personal adequacy.

Graph 4.29

Graphical representation showing correlation between compulsion and interpersonal adequacy.

Graph 4.30

Graphical representation showing correlation between compulsion and communication skills.

Table 4.27 Shows the results of correlation between Compulsion (dimension of smartphone addiction) and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills (dimensions of social competence).

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between compulsion and personal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.439, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between compulsion and personal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between compulsion and personal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between compulsion and interpersonal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.446, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between compulsion and interpersonal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between compulsion and interpersonal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between compulsion and Communication Skill. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.382, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between compulsion and Communication Skill. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the

correlation between compulsion and Communication Skill is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the H_{029} .

The results indicate a significant negative correlation between these factors, which is consistent with previous research on smartphone addiction and social competence. In summary, the results provide valuable insights into the impact of compulsion on social competence dimensions. The negative correlations observed between compulsion and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills underscore the importance of addressing smartphone addiction and its implications for social interactions. By understanding these relationships, researchers and practitioners can develop strategies to promote healthier technology use and enhance individuals' social competence in the digital age.

H₀₃₀: There is no significant correlation between forgetfulness and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.

Table 4.28

Summary of Correlation between Forgetfulness and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills

			Correlations			
			SA2- FORGETFU LLNESS	SC1- PERSO NAL ADEQ UACY	SC2- INTERPER SONAL ADEQUAC Y	SC3- COMMUNI CATION SKILL
Spear man's rho	SA2- FORGETFU LLNESS	Correl ation Coeffi cient	1.000	-.465**	-.459**	-.311**
		Sig. (2- tailed)	.	.000	.000	.001
		N	120	120	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Graph 4.31

Graphical representation showing correlation between forgetfulness and personal adequacy.

Graph 4.32

Graphical representation showing correlation between forgetfulness and interpersonal adequacy.

Graph 4.33

Graphical representation showing correlation between forgetfulness and communication skills.

Table 4.28 Shows the results of correlation between Forgetfulness (dimension of smartphone addiction) and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills (dimensions of social competence).

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Forgetfulness and personal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.465 , suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Forgetfulness and personal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01 , upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Forgetfulness and personal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Forgetfulness and

interpersonal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.459, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Forgetfulness and interpersonal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Forgetfulness and interpersonal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Forgetfulness and Communication Skill. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.311, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Forgetfulness and Communication Skill. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Forgetfulness and Communication Skill is statistically significant. Therefore we reject the H_0 .

The study's results show that there is a weak negative correlation between forgetfulness and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills among the participants. Ahirrao, K. D. (2023), the findings reveal that there is no significant disparity between genders in terms of interpersonal adequacy, communication skills, and overall social skills. It is crucial to address these issues to enhance social competence and overall well-being. The implications of these findings emphasize the importance of implementing interventions to tackle forgetfulness related to smartphone addiction. Strategies such as cognitive-behavioral therapy, mindfulness-based interventions, and memory training programs could help individuals improve memory strategies, boost self-efficacy, and enhance communication skills. By addressing forgetfulness and its impact on social

competence, individuals can develop healthier smartphone habits and strengthen their interpersonal relationships.

H₀₃₁: There is no significant correlation between lack of attention and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.

Table 4.29

Summary of Correlation between Lack of Attention and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills

Correlations

			SA3- LACK OF ATTENT ION	SC1- PERSON AL ADEQU ACY	SC2- INTERPERS ONAL ADEQUACY	SC3- COMMUNIC ATION SKILL
Spearman's rho	SA3- LACK OF ATTENT ION	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2- tailed)	1.000	-.397**	-.459**	-.436**
		N	120	120	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Graph 4.34

Graphical representation showing correlation between lack of attention and personal adequacy.

Graph 4.35

Graphical representation showing correlation between lack of attention and interpersonal adequacy.

Graph 4.36

Graphical representation showing correlation between lack of attention and communication skill.

Table 4.29 Shows the results of correlation between Lack of Attention (dimension of smartphone addiction) and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills (dimensions of social competence).

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Lack of Attention and personal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.397 , suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Lack of Attention and personal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01 , upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Lack of Attention and personal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Lack of Attention and interpersonal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.459, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Lack of Attention and interpersonal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Lack of Attention and interpersonal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Lack of Attention and Communication Skill. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.436, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Lack of Attention and Communication Skill. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Lack of Attention and Communication Skill is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the H_0 .

These results align with previous research on smartphone addiction, which has consistently shown its negative impact on various aspects of social competence. Therefore, it is crucial to address the issue of lack of attention related to smartphone addiction through interventions that focus on improving attentional control, enhancing interpersonal skills, and fostering effective communication strategies.

H₀₃₂: There is no significant correlation between depression and anxiety and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.

Table 4.30

Summary of Correlation between Depression & Anxiety and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills

Correlations

			SA4- DEPRES SION AND ANXIET Y	SC1- PERSON AL ADEQU ACY	SC2- INTERPERS ONAL ADEQUACY	SC3- COMMUNIC ATION SKILL
Spearm an's rho	SA4- DEPRES SION AND ANXIET Y	Correla tion Coeffic ient Sig. (2- tailed) N	1.000	-.394**	-.485**	-.353**
			.	.000	.000	.000
			120	120	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Graph 4.37

Graphical representation showing correlation between depression & anxiety and personal adequacy.

Graph 4.38

Graphical representation showing correlation between depression & anxiety and interpersonal adequacy.

Graph 4.39

Graphical representation showing correlation between depression & anxiety and communication skill.

Table 4.30 Shows the results of correlation between Depression and Anxiety (dimension of smartphone addiction) and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills (dimensions of social competence).

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Depression and Anxiety and personal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.394, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Depression and Anxiety and personal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Depression and Anxiety and personal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Depression and Anxiety and interpersonal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.485, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Depression and Anxiety and interpersonal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Depression and Anxiety and interpersonal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Depression and Anxiety and Communication Skill. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.353, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Depression and Anxiety and Communication

Skill. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Depression and Anxiety and Communication Skill is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the H_{032} .

The research findings indicate a weak negative relationship between depression and anxiety, and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills. This can be explained by psychodynamic theories, which suggest that feelings of inadequacy and low self-esteem are associated with these mental health challenges. Furthermore, social learning theories propose that individuals may develop ineffective communication patterns or struggle with assertiveness due to depression and anxiety. These findings emphasize the significance of addressing emotional well-being and enhancing social skills in mental health interventions, education, and workplace environments.

H₀₃₃: There is no significant correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.

Table 4.31

Summary of Correlation between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills

			Correlations			
			SA5- DISTURB ED HUNGER/ SLEEP	SC1- PERSO NAL ADEQU ACY	SC2- INTERPER SONAL ADEQUAC Y	SC3- COMMUNIC ATION SKILL
Spear man's rho	SA5- DISTURB ED HUNGER/ SLEEP	Correl ation Coeffi cient Sig. (2- tailed) N	1.000	-.469**	-.482**	-.375**
				.000	.000	.000
			120	120	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Graph 4.40

Graphical representation showing correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep and personal adequacy.

Graph 4.41

Graphical representation showing correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep and interpersonal adequacy.

Graph 4.42

Graphical representation showing correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep and communication skill.

Table 4.31 Shows the results of correlation between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep (dimension of smartphone addiction) and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills (dimensions of social competence).

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and personal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.469, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and personal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient,

it is evident that the correlation between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and personal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and interpersonal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.482, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and interpersonal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and interpersonal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and Communication Skill. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.375, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and Communication Skill. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and Communication Skill is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the H_0 .

The research highlights a weak negative correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep patterns and personal adequacy, interpersonal skills, and communication abilities. Disrupted hunger/sleep can affect cognitive functions and mood regulation, impacting how individuals interact with others and communicate effectively. These findings stress the significance of addressing sleep hygiene and nutrition to improve

overall well-being and social skills. By recognizing the impact of disturbed hunger/sleep on interpersonal relationships and communication skills, interventions in educational, health, and workplace settings can be better tailored to enhance social competence. It is crucial to understand the role of sleep and nutrition in influencing cognitive abilities and emotional well-being to promote healthier interactions and effective communication. In conclusion, the study underscores the importance of maintaining healthy eating and sleeping habits for optimal social functioning. By acknowledging the negative correlation between disrupted hunger/sleep and personal adequacy, interpersonal skills, and communication abilities, individuals can take proactive steps to improve their overall well-being and social competence. These results provide valuable insights for developing strategies and interventions aimed at enhancing social skills and fostering positive relationships in various settings.

H₀₃₄: There is no significant correlation between social withdrawal and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.

Table 4.32

Summary of Correlation between Social Withdrawal and Personal Adequacy, Interpersonal Adequacy, Communication Skills

Correlations

			SA6- WITHDR AWAL	SC1- PERSO NAL ADEQU ACY	SC2- INTERPERS ONAL ADEQUAC Y	SC3- COMMUNIC ATION SKILL
Spear man's rho	SA6- WITHDR AWAL	Correl ation Coeffi cient	1.000	-.507**	-.525**	-.436**
		Sig. (2- tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000
		N	120	120	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Graph 4.43

Graphical representation showing correlation between withdrawal and personal adequacy.

Graph 4.44

Graphical representation showing correlation between withdrawal and interpersonal adequacy.

Graph 4.45

Graphical representation showing correlation between withdrawal and communication skill.

Table 4.32 Shows the results of correlation between Social Withdrawal (dimension of smartphone addiction) and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills (dimensions of social competence).

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Social Withdrawal and personal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.507 , suggesting a Strong Negative correlation between Social Withdrawal and personal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01 , upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Social Withdrawal and personal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Social Withdrawal

and interpersonal adequacy. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.525, suggesting a Strong Negative correlation between Social Withdrawal and interpersonal adequacy. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Social Withdrawal and interpersonal adequacy is statistically significant.

Due to the non-normal distribution of the data, a Spearman Correlation and two-tailed test were employed to assess the relationship between Social Withdrawal and Communication Skill. The correlation coefficient indicates the degree of relationship between the two variables, with a coefficient of -0.436, suggesting a weak Negative correlation between Social Withdrawal and Communication Skill. With a significance value of 0.01, upon comparing it with the correlation coefficient, it is evident that the correlation between Social Withdrawal and Communication Skill is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the H_0 34.

The research uncovers a negative correlation between social withdrawal and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills. Factors like anxiety, depression, or introverted tendencies can all play a role in causing social withdrawal, which in turn affects personal adequacy and relationships with others. The absence of social connections can impede the development of effective communication skills, as demonstrated by the results of this study. It is crucial to address these issues through interventions that focus on enhancing social skills, boosting self-confidence, and encouraging active participation in social activities. By doing so, the detrimental impact of social withdrawal on social competence can be minimized, especially in educational and clinical settings where these skills are essential for success. In conclusion, the findings emphasize the significance of

interventions that target social skills training and self-esteem building to counteract the negative consequences of social withdrawal. By addressing the root causes of social isolation and providing support to individuals struggling with social interactions, it is possible to improve their overall social competence. These interventions can have a positive impact on personal adequacy, interpersonal relationships, and communication skills, ultimately leading to better outcomes in both educational and clinical environments.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary:

The study examined the interplay between smartphone addiction, social competence, personality types, and gender. A significant negative correlation was found between smartphone addiction and social competence, wherein individuals with higher levels of smartphone addiction tended to exhibit lower social competence. However, neither personality type (Type A, Type B, Type A-B) nor gender (male or female) had a significant effect on the mean levels of social competence or smartphone addiction. Additionally, there was no significant interaction effect of personality type and gender on the mean level of smartphone addiction. The study did not find any significant differences in the mean scores of various smartphone addiction factors (compulsion, forgetfulness, lack of attention, depression/anxiety, disturbed hunger/sleep, social withdrawal) or social competence factors (personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, communication skills) across genders or personality types. Notably, significant positive correlations were observed between the various smartphone addiction factors and social competence factors, indicating that higher levels of smartphone addiction are associated with lower levels of social competence. Overall, the findings highlight the significant relationship between smartphone addiction and social competence.

5.2 Conclusions:

1. H₀₁ There is a significant correlation between smartphone addiction and social competence.
2. H₀₂ There is no significant difference in the mean level of social competence among

participants with type A, type B and type A-B personality.

3. H₀₃ There is no significant difference in the mean level of social competence among male and female participants.

4. H₀₄ There is no significant difference in the mean level of smartphone Addiction among participants with type A, type B and type A-B personalities.

5. H₀₅ There is no significant difference in the mean level of smartphone Addiction among male and female participants.

6. H₀₆ There is no significant interaction effect of personality type and gender on the mean level of smartphone Addiction.

7. H₀₇ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of smartphone addiction among males of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

8. H₀₈ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of smartphone addiction among females of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

9. H₀₉ There is no significant difference in the means scores of social competence among males of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

10. H₀₁₀ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social competence among females of Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

11. H₀₁₁ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of compulsion of males and females.

12. H₀₁₂ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of forgetfulness of males and females.

13. H₀₁₃ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of lack of attention of males and females.

14. H₀₁₄ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of depression & anxiety of males and females.

15. H₀₁₅ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of disturbed hunger/sleep of males and females.

16. H₀₁₆ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social withdrawal of males and females.

17. H₀₁₇ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of personal adequacy of males and females.

18. H₀₁₈ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of interpersonal adequacy of males and females.

19. H₀₁₉ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of communication skills of males and females.

20. H₀₂₀ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of compulsion among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

21. H₀₂₁ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of forgetfulness among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

22. H₀₂₂ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of lack of attention among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

23. H₀₂₃ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of depression and anxiety among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.

24. H₀₂₄ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of disturbed hunger/sleep among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
25. H₀₂₅ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of social withdrawal among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
26. H₀₂₆ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of personal adequacy among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
27. H₀₂₇ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of interpersonal adequacy among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
28. H₀₂₈ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of communication skills among Type A, Type B and Type A-B Personality.
29. H₀₂₉ There is a significant correlation between compulsion and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
30. H₀₃₀ There is a significant correlation between forgetfulness and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
31. H₀₃₁ There is a significant correlation between lack of attention and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
32. H₀₃₂ There is a significant correlation between depression and anxiety and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
33. H₀₃₃ There is a significant correlation between disturbed hunger/sleep and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.
34. H₀₃₄ There is a significant correlation between social withdrawal and personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills.

5.3 Implications:

Individuals facing challenges with smartphone addiction may initially resist seeking professional help or participating in support groups due to denial, stigma, or fear of being judged. Implementing workplace policies and initiatives may face resistance from employees who are heavily reliant on their smartphones or unwilling to change their habits. Parents and caregivers may struggle to establish healthy smartphone boundaries within the family due to their own addiction or lack of awareness about the impact on social competence. Integrating smartphone addiction screening and social competence evaluations into existing mental health and social services may require additional training, resources, and funding. Tech companies may prioritize profit over societal well-being, potentially hindering efforts to promote responsible technology use and social competence.

5.4 Limitations:

The study did not take into account the differentiation between different types of smartphone activities or the specific contexts in which smartphones were utilized. In real-world scenarios, the impact on social aptitude may vary depending on the nature of smartphone usage. For instance, the effects of using smartphones primarily for communication purposes, such as messaging or video calls, may differ from those of using them predominantly for entertainment or gaming activities.

The study sample may not be representative of the broader population, limiting the generalizability of the findings. Future research should aim to replicate the study with diverse samples from different cultural, socioeconomic, and geographical backgrounds.

The study did not account for potential confounding variables, such as the amount of time spent on specific smartphone activities (e.g., social media, gaming, browsing), the presence of pre-existing social difficulties, or other lifestyle factors that could influence both smartphone addiction and social competence.

The study relied on self-report measures, which may be subject to biases such as social desirability or recall errors. Future studies could incorporate objective measures or observational data to complement self-report measures and enhance the validity of the findings.

The study failed to consider the possible existence of comorbidities or underlying mental health issues that might affect both smartphone addiction and social skills. People with conditions like anxiety, depression, or social anxiety disorder could display varying behaviors in terms of smartphone usage and social interactions, potentially altering the perceived correlation between the two.

The specific socioeconomic and environmental contexts of the participants could impose limitations on the study's findings. Factors like the accessibility of technology, educational background, and living conditions have the potential to influence both the patterns of smartphone usage and the opportunities for social interactions. As a result, the generalizability of the results across diverse populations may be compromised.

5.5 Recommendations:

Counsellors and therapists can employ evidence-based strategies and techniques to help individuals develop healthier habits, manage compulsive behaviors, and enhance their social aptitude. Support groups provide a supportive environment for overcoming smartphone addiction.

Corporate policies promoting responsible smartphone use and work-life balance can create a healthier work environment. Initiatives like digital detox sessions, team-building activities, and communication skills training foster face-to-face interactions and enhance social competence among colleagues.

With access to resources and support, parents can demonstrate healthy smartphone behaviors and cultivate positive social skills in young individuals. Family interventions, such as setting limits, prioritizing quality time, and promoting social engagement, can effectively nurture social competence.

By incorporating these assessments, mental health and social service professionals can better address the complex challenges faced by individuals in today's digital age. Tailored interventions and programs can assist in improving social functioning and overall well-being.

Partnerships with tech companies can leverage their expertise and resources to launch initiatives that instill healthy digital habits and nurture real-world relationships. Collaborative efforts can enhance societal well-being and promote a balanced reliance on digital devices.

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Appendices

Appendix 1	Permission Letter
Appendix 2	Consent Form and Personal Details
Appendix 3	Questionnaires used in the Study

Appendix 1**Permission Letter**

ST. XAVIER'S COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS)

Re-accredited with 'A' (CGPA 3.41 out of 4) by NAAC (3rd Cycle) | Affiliated to Gujarat University

February 8, 2024

To whomsoever it may concern

This is to certify that Mr Ayan Saiyed is a student of MA Psychology Semester 4 (Roll No.: 22-PPS-025) at St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Ahmedabad. As part of the course, he is working on his dissertation under the guidance of Dr. Tatpar Joshipura. The title of his dissertation is "*The Impact of Personality Type and Gender on Smartphone Addiction and Social Competence of Young Adults.*" The data is meant for research purposes only and will not be misused in any way. Kindly allow him to collect responses for the same.

Your cooperation will be highly appreciated.

Dr. Profaina Christian
Head,
Psychology Department

Dr. Tatpar Joshipura
Research Guide
Psychology Department

Principal
Principal
St. Xavier's College (Autonomous)
Ahmedabad - 380 009.

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Appendix 2**Consent Form and Personal Details**

Consent Form

Greetings for the day!!

I, Ayan Saiyed, a Master's Clinical Psychology student at St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Ahmedabad.

This research is being conducted as part of my Master's degree dissertation, under the guidance of Dr. Tatpar Joshipura. Your participation requires you to complete the questionnaire given. You have to select the option which best describes you. There are no right or wrong answers. It would not require more than 15-20 minutes of your time. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw at any given point in time. Your identity as a participant will remain completely confidential- by including an initial of your name or a pseudo name. All your responses shall remain confidential and will be used only for research purposes.

Name: Age: Gender: Male Female Other
(Optional)

Educational Qualification: Last Semester GPA:

Medium: English Gujarati Family Type: Joint Nuclear

Socioeconomic Status:

Upper-Class	☐
Upper Middle-Class	☐
Middle-Class	☐
Lower Middle-Class	☐
Lower-Class	☐

I have read and understood all the instructions mentioned and give my full consent to be a participant in this research.

Signature:
(Only Initials)

Date:

Appendix 3**Questionnaires Used in the Study**

Sr. No.	STATEMENTS	Strongly Agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Score
---------	------------	----------------	-------	-----------	----------	-------------------	-------

FORM-A

- | | | | | | | | |
|-----|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| 1. | I prefer to move around rapidly when I am not doing anything. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 2. | I prefer to finish the tasks at hand as soon as possible | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 3. | I am never late if I have an appointment. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 4. | I tend to feel impatient with the rate at which most events take place. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 5. | I have very few interests outside my work. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 6. | I feel impatient when I don't have any work in hand. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 7. | I always feel rushed. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 8. | I am habitual of having quick meals. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 9. | Competition is my first choice. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 10. | I enjoy doing two or more things simultaneously. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 11. | Quantity is a measure of success for me. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 12. | I cannot relax without guilt. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 13. | I have always been struggling to achieve more in less time. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 14. | I am very particular to exhibit my superiority whenever I play. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 15. | I have always lived the life of deadlines. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 16. | I take it as a privilege to display or discuss my achievements or accomplishments whenever I get an opportunity to do so. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |
| 17. | I have never found time sufficient for the task at hand. | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ | ☐ |

Factors	I				II		III			IV			V			VI	
Item No.	8	10	13	15	2	6	4	7	17	3	9	16	1	11	14	5	12
Raw Score																	
Total Score																	

Sr. No.	STATEMENTS	Strongly Agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Score
FORM-B							
1.	I do not work under time pressure.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
2.	I do not display or discuss either my achievements or accomplishments unless such exposure is demanded by the situation.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
3.	I have never set deadlines for my accomplishments.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
4.	I play for fun and relaxation.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
5.	I relax whenever I want to do so.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
6.	I do not give much weightage to quantity in comparison to other measures of success.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
7.	I prefer to concentrate on one task at a time.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
8.	I enjoy my food by making no haste while eating.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
9.	I never feel rushed.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
10.	Leisure time is welcome after a spell of work.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
11.	I am open in expressing my feelings.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
12.	I have many interests outside my work.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
13.	I am comfortable with the rate at which most events take place.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
14.	I take appointments casually.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
15.	I prefer to complete the tasks at hand slowly.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
16.	I prefer to sit at one place when I am not doing anything.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>

Factors	I				II			III			IV			V		
Item No.	5	14	15	16	4	7	12	2	10	13	1	3	8	6	9	11
Raw Score																
Total Score																

Sr. No.	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agre	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1.	It becomes hard for me to be away from my phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
2.	I feel anxious and irritated without my phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
3.	I don't like to meet anyone while using my phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
4.	Instead of looking and observing the outer world, I like to surf in my Phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
5.	I surf in my phone without any reason.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
6.	I forget things due to excess use of my phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
7.	I am unable to concentrate on academic related activities.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
8.	I frequently skip my meal due to phone even if I feel hungry.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
9.	I generally forget to do my homework due to phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
10.	While studying I wish to keep my phone with me.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
11.	I don't take my food without my phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
12.	I spend less time with my family members and friends due to phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
13.	While sleeping I wake up suddenly and check my phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
14.	I don't feel hungry while using my phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Sr. No.	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agre	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree
15.	I am unable to sleep easily because I feel there will be messages for me.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
16.	I feel there is no other source of entertainment except phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
17.	I feel lonely and pity without my phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
18.	I have more friends on social media than in real life.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
19.	I can't focus during the lectures in class because I feel I'll check it later in phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
20.	Generally my phone has low battery due to excess use.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
21.	My family members and friends say that I over use my phone.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
22.	I frequently chat with my online friends for a long time.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
23.	I always have my smart phone in my mind.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Sr. No.	STATEMENT	Always	Mostly	Sometimes	Never	Score
I						
1.	I have positive outlook towards life.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
2.	I feel that the course I have adopted will prove worthless in future.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☒ <input type="text"/>
3.	I desperately want to change the way I look.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☒ <input type="text"/>
4.	I can accomplish my tasks independently.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
5.	I don't bother what people think about me.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
6.	I learn from my experiences.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
7.	I seek others help while taking decisions.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
8.	I cooperate with others.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
9.	I think more about my failures than my successes.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☒ <input type="text"/>
10.	I worry a lot that I am ineffective and incompetent.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☒ <input type="text"/>
11.	I get irritated if someone opposes me.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☒ <input type="text"/>
12.	I speak whatever comes to my mind without thinking.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☒ <input type="text"/>
13.	I do not like to take instructions.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☒ <input type="text"/>
14.	I admit my mistakes and apologize for them.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
15.	I control my temper when people are angry with me.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
16.	I easily get frustrated.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☒ <input type="text"/>
17.	I get annoyed when criticized.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☒ <input type="text"/>
Total Score Dimension I						<input type="text"/>

Sr. No.	STATEMENT	Always	Mostly	Sometimes	Never	Score
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II

18.	I am self disciplined.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
19.	I am considered a disruptive student.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
20.	I am usually not clear how to interact with people from other cultures.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
21.	I follow the socially acceptable greetings.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
22.	I show respect for teachers and neighbours.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
23.	I maintain acceptable social distance while interacting with others.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
24.	I hesitate to interact with people of opposite sex.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
25.	I avoid eye contact during conversation.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
26.	I can address a gathering confidently.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
27.	I feel embarrassed and scared in a group of new people.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
28.	I get easily annoyed with others.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
29.	I usually get into arguments to prove my point.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
30.	I have good understanding and warm relationships with my friends.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
31.	I get provoked into quarrelling with others.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
32.	I get along well with other children.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
33.	I try to resolve conflicts amicably.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
34.	I am always there when my friends need me.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>

Total Score Dimension II

Sr. No.	STATEMENT	Always	Mostly	Sometimes	Never	Score
III						
35.	I find it difficult to talk effectively.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
36.	I can express my views appropriately to others.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
37.	I use suitable gestures while talking.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
38.	I can easily communicate with my teachers.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
39.	I can participate in discussions.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
40.	I have difficulty starting a conversation.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
41.	I am unable to speak up in front of a gathering.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
42.	I have difficulty in making my voice heard.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
43.	I can join ongoing discussions.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
44.	I continue talking even after others lose interest.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
45.	I ask my teachers without hesitation for clarification of a point.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
46.	I listen to others point of view without interrupting them.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
47.	I can start a conversation with my classmates.	☐	☐	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
Total Score Dimension III						<input type="text"/>